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**SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSES OF
REPRESENTATIVE REGIONS**

(BASELINE STUDY)

**THE CASE OF CENTRAL GONJA AND NABDAM DISTRICTS OF
GHANA**

Final Report

**(Appendix D of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env.
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ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CGD	Central Gonja District
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
GD	Green Deal
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
HHH(s)	Household Head(s)
KIIs	Key Informant Interviews
ND	Nabdam District
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organization(s)
WiHH(s)	Women in Household(s)

CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

1.1 The CIRAWA Project

CIRAWA – Agroecological Strategies for Resilient Farming in West Africa, is an EU-funded project, which aims to “unlock the potential of agro-ecology in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices”. CIRAWA is working on innovative agroecological approaches using, among others, the following strategies:

- 1) valorisation of agro-wastes and bio-based fertiliser production;
- 2) production of high-quality seeds;
- 3) saline soil reclamation through phytoremediation; and
- 4) soil fertility, water, and crop management practices.

These strategies are being deployed in 4 countries in West Africa; Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal, and The Gambia.

The CIRAWA Project (and three similar ones in North, East, and Central Africa) arose out of the EU-AU collaborative efforts in agriculture and the focus of the EU to facilitate a green transition according to its Green Deal (GD) objectives, which basically define the EU’s climate strategy to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It is also in line with the EU-Africa biodiversity strategy which seeks to create a circular economy.

Even though the original proposal indicated that certain specific activities would be undertaken in the different countries, it has been pointed out and agreed that almost all the proposed intervention activities are required in all the countries. Thus, the following activities are expected to be undertaken in the various countries in consultation with farmers with regard to their needs and requirements.

- 1) Characterisation of local soils: fertility studies
- 2) Characterisation of locally available manures and crop residues, protocol definition and implementation and production of innovative vermicompost and bio-based fertilisers
- 3) Characterisation of locally available crop residues and production of materials for household energy production.
- 4) Soil conservation practices
- 5) Saline soil reclamation strategies through an integrated approach based on salt-tolerant species (phytoremediation)
- 6) Crop management decision support system: irrigation, and fertilisation modules.
- 7) High-quality seed production and multiplication, with consideration given to characterization and improvements of seeds of indigenous crops.
- 8) Water collection techniques: cloud/fog harvesting.

- 9) Strategies to increase access of farmers to markets.
- 10) Awareness creation campaigns to promote agro-ecological farming systems.
- 11) Farming system cross-border best-practices integration platform
- 12) Promoting participatory and inclusive governance, especially for women and youth.

In Ghana, Central Gonja District in the Savannah Region and Nabdam District in the Upper East Region were chosen for the implementation of the CIRAWA project. The Central Gonja District is in the Guinea Savannah agroecological zone and is sparsely populated (per square kilometer) and the Nabdam District is in the Sudan Savannah agroecological zone and is thickly populated (per square kilometer).

1.2 Study Area

The Republic of Ghana is one of the countries in West Africa occupying a total area of 238,540 km² with a population density of 140 persons per sq km in 2022. Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood for many Ghanaians, employing about 52% of the workforce and accounting for about 54% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Agriculture is predominantly smallholder, traditional, and rain-fed.

In Ghana the project was undertaken in two unique zones; the Guinea Savannah and Sudan Savannah ecosystems represented by the Central Gonja in the Savannah Region and the Nabdam District in the Upper East Region respectively. These locations were specifically chosen because of the distinct characteristics that each site possesses, in terms of the fertility of the soils, acreage available for farming, farming systems, ecological zones, and population pressure among others.

The Central Gonja District is one of the seven (7) metropolitan and municipal assemblies in the Savannah Region. The district is located at the southern end of the Northern Region of Ghana and covers a total land area of 8,353 Km². It has Buipe as its administrative capital. The population of the District according to the 2021 population and housing census stands at 142,762 with 71,635 males and 71,127 females.

The Nabdam District is one of the fifteen (15) Municipalities and Districts in the Upper East Region. It covers a total land area of 251km² and the Administrative capital as Nangodi. The population of the District according to the 2021 population and housing census stands at 51,861 with 25,552 males and 26,309 females.

Climate and Vegetation

The Central Gonja and the Nabdam District like the other parts of Ghana, fall under a tropical climate and are characterized by two main seasons (Wet and Dry) distinct by the rainfall received. Typically for the northern sector of Ghana where the two districts are located, a single rainy season occurs. The monthly rainfall totals rise slowly from March with a check in June or July until a maximum is reached in August or September. Thereafter, they sharply decrease. An average annual of 950mm and a maximum temperature of 45⁰C. However, the dry season usually occurs from October to March a very long period, and has a minimum temperature of 12⁰C in December (GSS 2012). The Central Gonja District in the Savannah Region has more

rainfall of about 1200 mm yearly while the Nabdam District in the Upper East Region has less rainfall of about 800-1000 mm yearly (GSS 2021).

The Guinea Savannah ecosystem (Central Gonja District) in Ghana starts from the northern limit of the forest zone emerging out of the dry semideciduous forest (fire zone subtype). The less disturbed area of the Guinea Savannah ecosystem is dominated by relatively short trees with shrub and scrub undergrowth. The Sudan Savannah ecosystem (Nabdam District) is located to the north of the Guinea Savanna. The vegetation is mainly isolated short trees, scrub, and short grass undergrowth. Nabdam District has less vegetative cover whereas Central Gonja has a large vegetative cover (GSS 2012). The most communal beneficial trees for both districts are ebony, baobab, dawadawa, and shea nuts which serve as a source of income for the natives.

Topography and Drainage

Central Gonja District lies within latitude 8°32' and 10°2' North and longitude 1°5' and 2° 58' West. The lands in Central Gonja District are low-lying and gently undulating at altitudes between 150m to 300m above sea level even though some parts average 600m (MoFA, 2020). The district is drained by two major rivers namely the White Volta and Black Volta. The Nabdam District lies between longitudes 0.31° and 10.50° West and latitudes 10.15° and 10.60° North. The land in the Nabdam District is dominated by relatively undulating lowlands, and gentle slopes ranging from one percent to five percent gradient with some isolated rock outcrops and some upland slopes. The District is drained by the Red and White Volta lake and their tributaries.

Land Use and Soils

The soil in the Central Gonja District is very fertile and rich in nutrients but mostly savanna ochrosols, alluvial, and laterite. Farmers in this district also rear livestock, farm around riverbanks, and are mostly into fishing. The soil is good for cultivating rice, cowpeas, maize, groundnuts, vegetables, and others. The land in the Nabdam District is the cornerstone of agriculture in the district and it is made up of different kinds of rocks such as sandstone, granite, tarkwaian, voltaria, quartzite, gneiss, and birimian rocks. Some parts of the district are known to have gold. The soils are mostly sandy, gravel, and clayey soils with a little bit of loamy soil present, which makes it difficult for farmers during crop production. The soil is well suited for the cultivation of millet, sorghum, and other crops. Farmers in Nabdam also rear livestock.

1.3 Objectives of Work Package 2 (the Baseline Survey)

The overall objective of WP2 is for qualitative and quantitative assessment of farmers' and communities' needs and requirements, and their resource availability and use as well as identification of the available agro-ecological practices taking place in the different locations and how they are adapted to local needs and contexts. It also provides baseline information on social, economic, and environmental indicators against which project progress and effectiveness during implementation can be monitored and evaluated.

1.4 Methodology (Brief on Sampling and Data Collection and Analyses)

Qualitative and quantitative research designs were used in the information and data collection from various people in the two districts. Focus group discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs) were used to collect most of the qualitative information while in-depth household interviews were used to collect most of the quantitative information. Data collection protocols were designed and used to solicit information from farmers and other stakeholders on farmers' requirements and needs as part of the socio-economic and environmental baseline survey. It involved the use of enumerators and supervisors who are conversant with the different environments and the languages spoken by the people. They, however, had to be trained in the data collection process so that they could interact effectively to tease out the important requirements and needs of farmers and community members. WACWISA-UDS and FIDEP Foundation teams trained the supervisors and enumerators and participated in some of the field activities.

Table 1.1 shows the numbers of communities and households sampled from the two districts. The focus groups were composed of males and females. In the case of the household interviews, both men and women were interviewed independently in order to capture intra-household gender information. In each household, the head of household (HHH) and a woman in the household (WiHH) were interviewed. There were no women-headed households in the sample.

Communities and respondents were sampled using a three-stage sampling procedure. The districts (Central Gonja and Nabdam) were first stratified according to agricultural operational zones. Those constituted the strata. Simple random sampling was then used in the second stage to sample the required number of communities from the strata. Five (5) communities were sampled by this process from each district. In the third stage, systematic random sampling was used to choose five (5) households in each community for interview. Thus, there were 10 respondents from each community (5 men and 5 women) (see Table 1.1).

Table 1
.1: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs, and household interviews that were undertaken.

District	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Adults)	Number of Focus Group Discussions (Youth)	Number of Key Informant Interviews	Household interviews	
				Men	Women
Central Gonja	10	5	5	25	25
Nabdam	9	5	5	25	25
Total	19	10	10	50	50

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

Chapter 2

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HOUSEHOLD HEADS

2.1 Characteristics of Household Heads (HHHs) and Members

Men are usually household heads. A woman can claim to be a household head only when there is no adult male in the house. So, there are cases where women are de facto heads of households but still prefer to leave that title to a male adult in the household. It is therefore no wonder that both men (HHH) and women (WiHH) agree that almost all households in both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts are men (Table 2.1)

Table 2.1: Men and women- headed households in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts

District	As reported by Men (through HHH questionnaire)				As reported by Women (through the WiHH questionnaire)			
	Men headed households		Women headed households		Men headed households		Women headed households	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja	18	100.0	0	0.0	24	96.0	1	4.0
Nabdam	25	100.0	0	0.0	24	96.0	1	4.0

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

Table 2.2 shows that the farmers in both districts are largely indigenes: about 96% in Central Gonja and about 94% in Nabdam. The implication is that local regulations including land and tree tenure should not be a constraint to farm level decision- making,

Table 2.2: Indigene status of farmers in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts.

District	As reported by Men (HHH)				As reported by Women			
	Indigenes		Non-indigenes		Indigenes		Non-indigenes	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja	24	96.0	1	4.0	19	76.0	6	24.0
Nabdam	23	92.0	2	8.0	20	80.0	5	20.0

The average ages of the men respondents (household heads) in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts are 42.9 years and 53.2 years respectively with relatively low standard deviations as shown in Table 2.3. The corresponding average ages of their spouses are 38.0 years and 42.7 years respectively. Since household heads (HHHs) are usually the oldest in the HHs, the indication is that the farming population in the districts is relatively youthful. This debunks the widely claimed assertion that only old people are those farming in Ghana. There are a considerable number of youth (both men and women) on the farms in Ghana and other parts of West Africa. There are some old farmers in the communities as the maximum ages encountered indicate (Table 2.3) but relatively young farmers are much more.

Table 2.3: Average ages of HHHs and spouses

District	Ages (years) of HHHs (Men)				Ages (years) of their spouses (women)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central Gonja	42.9	9.6	64	30	38.0	9.6	65	25
Nabdham	53.2	11.6	75	35	42.7	9.3	64	27
Both Districts	48.9	11.9	75	30	39.7	9.7	65	25

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

Table 2.4 indicates that the relatively young farmers have considerable experience in farming: an average of about 23 years in Central Gonja and 27 years in Nabdam. Other factors remaining constant, a youthful population, that has considerable experience in farming, is likely to be more eager to try new ideas and adopt progressive technologies especially technologies that build on their indigenous knowledge.

Table 2.4: Crop farming experiences of HHHs

District	Crop farming experience (HHHs)			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
Central Gonja	23.4	11.1	60	6
Nabdham	27.1	11.1	57	4

Source: Field survey, April 2023

About 92% of the male farmers and about 72% of female farmers (their wives) have been in their present locations for over 20 years in the districts (Table 2.5). It implies that both men and women respondents are very conversant with the farming history as well as the agricultural production and livelihood dynamics of the area.

Table 2.5: Length of time HHHs (men) and WiHHs (women) have been in the Districts

Districts	< 5 years		5 – 10 years		11 – 20 years		> 20 years	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Men (HHH)								
Central Gonja	0	0	0	0	2	8	23	92.0
Nabdham	1	3.7	0	0	1	3.7	25	92.6
Both Districts	1	1.9	0	0	3	5.8	48	92.3
Women (WiHH)								
Central Gonja	0	0	1	4.0	4	16.0	20	80.0
Nabdham	1	4.0	2	8.0	6	24.0	16	64.0
Both Districts	1	2.0	3	6.0	10	20.0	36	72.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The educational status of HHHs and their spouses is given in Table 2.6. About 39% of HHHs (men) and about 44% of spouses (women) in the Central Gonja District have not had any form of formal classroom instruction. In the case of Nabdam District, it is much higher, 60% for

men and their spouses. These figures are quite surprising because it is common knowledge that women's education lags behind men, generally, and more so in Moslem-dominated environments. It, however, seems to be different with this result. If pre-school and non-formal education are regarded as "no formal classroom" education, the percentages will be 72.2% for men and 70.3% for women in the Central Gonja District while that for Nabdam District it will be 68.0% for men and 80.0% for women. That does not still explain the situation, especially with respect to Central Gonja District. There is a need for deeper investigations as to what is responsible for the unexpected result.

Table 2.6: Educational status of HHHs and spouses

	Central Gonja District				Nabdam District			
	HHHs		Spouses		HHHs		Spouses	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Pre-School	2	11.1	6	22.2	2	8.0	3	20.0
Primary	1	5.6	4	14.8	2	8.0	2	13.3
JHS/MSLC	1	11.1	2	7.4	1	4.0	3	6.7
SHS/Technical /O&A-Levels	2	5.6	1	3.7	3	12.0	0	0
Tertiary	1	5.6	1	3.7	2	8.0	0	0
Non-formal (completed)	1	5.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
Non-formal (Not completed)	3	16.7	1	3.7	0	0	0	0
None (no form of classroom instructions)	7	38.9	12	44.4	15	60.0	9	60.0
Total	18	100.0	27	100.0	25	100.0	17	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Household (HH) size distributions in the districts are presented in Table 2.7 and Figure 2.1. The average household size in Central Gonja District is 8.3 (with a standard deviation of 1.1) and that of Nabdam District is lower, 7.8 with a standard deviation of 1.2. This implies the household size ranges are about 7 to 10 in Central Gonja and about 6 to 8 in Nabdam.

Table 2.7: Average household size distributions

District		Male adults	Female adults	Male children	Female children	Total HH size
Central Gonja	Average	1.9	2.6	2.0	1.8	8.3
	Std. Dev.	0.8	1.3	1.2	0.9	1.1
	Max.	4	6	5	3	-
	Min.	1	1	1	1	-
Nabdam	Average	2.5	2.2	1.7	1.4	7.8
	Std. Dev.	1.4	1.2	0.9	0.6	1.2
	Max.	6	5	4	3	-
	Min.	1	1	1	1	-
Total (both Districts)	Average	2.2	2.4	1.8	1.5	7.9
	Std. Dev.	1.1	1.2	1.0	0.7	1.1
	Max.	6	6	5	3	-
	Min.	1	1	1	1	-

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

Figure 2.1: Average household size distributions

The different categories of household members in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts contribute to farming and other household activities in different ways and in different proportions as given in Tables 2.8 and 2.9. There are interesting differences in the division of labour in the two districts.

Male adults are almost wholly responsible for land preparation and weeding in Central Gonja District but they share planting and harvesting almost equally with female adults (Table 2.8). Carrying of water and firewood is however the responsibility of female adults and female

children in the Central Gonja District as shown in the table. Female adults and male children also undertake most of the household errands.

In the Nabdam District female adults undertake some land preparation and weeding (about 19% and 16% respectively) but most of the two farm activities are done by male adults (about 76% and 78% respectively) (Table 2.9). The table also shows that male adults and female adults share planting and harvesting activities almost equally. The feeding and shepherding of livestock is shared between male adults, female adults, and male children. Female adults, male children and female children have the responsibility of carrying water while female adults and female children are those that provide (carry) firewood for the households (Table 2.9).

Table 2.8: HH members' contributions to farming and other activities (Central Gonja District)

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	36	97.3	1	2.7	0	0.0	0	0.0	37
Planting	37	42.5	45	51.7	3	3.5	2	2.3	87
Weeding	42	93.3	1	2.2	2	4.4	0	0.0	45
Harvesting	44	46.3	46	48.4	4	4.2	1	1.1	95
Feeding animals	0	0	3	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3
Errands	9	18	18	36.0	15	30.0	8	16.0	50
Carrying water	0	0	55	84.6	0	0.0	10	15.4	65
Carrying firewood	0	0	55	85.9	0	0.0	9	14.1	64
No farm contribution	0	0	0	0	3	50.0	3	50.0	6

Source: Field Survey, May 2023

Table 2.9: HH members contributions to farming and other activities (Nabdam District)

	Male Adults		Female Adults		Male Children		Female Children		Total Freq
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	
Land preparation	57	76.0	14	18.7	4	5.3	0	0.0	75
Planting	49	50.5	45	46.7	0	0.0	3	3.1	97
Weeding	50	78.1	10	15.6	3	4.7	1	1.6	64
Harvesting	51	53.1	42	43.8	0	0.0	3	3.1	96
Feeding animals	30	57.7	10	19.2	10	19.2	2	3.9	52
Shepherding livestock	9	34.6	3	11.5	12	46.2	2	7.7	26
Errands	16	30.2	14	26.4	14	26.4	9	17.0	53
Carrying water	2	4.0	30	60.0	9	18.0	9	18.0	50
Carrying firewood	2	9.5	13	61.9	0	0.0	6	28.6	21
No farm contribution	0	0.0	1	7.1	3	21.4	10	71.4	14
Other	0	0.0	1	9.1	4	36.4	6	54.6	11

2.2 Major and Minor Occupations of HHHs and Spouses

Tables 2.10 and 2.11 give the major and minor occupations of HHHs and their spouses in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts respectively. As indicated, arable crop farming is the main occupation for all the people, men and women, in both districts. Livestock and tree crop farming are the main minor occupations for men in the Central Gonja District, while livestock and arable crop farming are the main minor occupations for men in the Nabdam District.

In the case of women in the Central Gonja District, the main minor occupations are livestock farming, tree produce processing, and petty trading/food vending (Table 2.10). The main minor occupation for women in the Nabdam District is petty trading/food vending (Table 2.11). What the results indicate is that the livelihood of the people in the two districts is critically linked to farming. Even the marketing and processing of farm produce are not important activities in the districts. There is a need to promote some kinds of agribusinesses so that some educated youth can be attracted to undertake farm ventures in the districts.

Table 2.10: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (Central Gonja District)

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (%)	Freq.	Freq (%)	Freq.
Arable crop farming	17 (94.4)	4 (36.4)	23 (88.5)	5 (27.8)
Tree crop farming	-	2 (18.2)	-	-
Livestock farming		3 (27.3)	1 (3.8)	4 (27.2)
Produce marketing (Crop)				1 (5.6)
Livestock marketing (incl. produce)	-	-	1 (3.8)	-
Tree produce processing (e.g. shea, dawadawa, baobab etc.)	-	-	-	4 (22.2)
Petty trading/food vending	-	1 (9.1)	1 (3.8)	4 (22.2)
Salaried worker	1 (5.6)		-	-
Other	-	1 (9.1)	-	-
Total	18 (100.0)	11 (100.0)	26 (100.0)	18 (100.0)

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

Table 2.11: Major and minor occupations of HHHs and spouses (Nabdram District)

Occupations	HHHs (men)		Spouses of HHHs (women)	
	Major occupation	Minor occupation	Major occupation	Minor occupation
	Freq (%)	Freq.	Freq (%)	Freq.
Arable crop farming	22 (88.0)	10 (40.0)	11 (73.3)	8 (61.6)
Livestock farming	-	10 (40.0)	-	1 (7.7)
Petty trading/food vending		4 (16.0)	2 (13.3)	4 (30.8)
Salaried worker	2 (8.0)	-	-	-
Tradesman (bricklayer, carpenter, tailor, etc.)	-	1 (4.0)	1 (6.7)	-
Artisan (basket weaver, potter, etc.)	1 (4.0)	-	1 (6.7)	-
Total	25 (100.0)	25 (100.0)	15 (100.0)	13 (100.0)

Source: Field Survey, April 2023

2.3 Farm Sizes and Types

2.3.1 Household and individual farm sizes

Table 2.12 gives the average farm sizes of households, “individual men farms” and “individual women farms”. The distinction is made between “household (HH) farms”, “individual men farms” and “individual women farms”. The three components add up to give the “household farm holdings”. Household farms are those managed by the HHH. They are held in trust for all

members of the HH. The different farm sizes are shown in diagram form in Figure 2.2. The Table and Figure show the wide differences in farm sizes between the two districts. Farm sizes in the Central Gonja District are about four times the sizes in the Nabdam District. That reflects the relative population pressure and farmland availability in the two districts. They also show the differences between individual men's and individual women's farm sizes. In Central Gonja District individual men's farms are about three times individual women's farm sizes while in Nabdam District the difference is quite small. Farmland is abundant in Central Gonja District.

In Central Gonja District, all farms, especially the HH farms, are located quite far from settlements. It is the opposite in Nabdam District. Most HH farms in Nabdam District are “compound farms” and are usually located around the houses. It is the individual men's and women's farm plots that are usually some distance from the homes, thus they are termed “bush” farms. Members of the HHs contribute labour to the HH farms and also partake in what is produced from the farms as a right. The individual farms belong exclusively to whoever cultivates them. They may help one another on their individual farms but it is not mandatory. The produce from those farms belongs to the individuals. Cash crops are often cultivated on individual farms by both men and women.

On average in the survey area, farm sizes are 17.2 acres, 9.7 acres, and 3.2 acres for household (HH), individual men, and individual women farms respectively in Central Gonja District while they are 4.6 acres, 1.6 acres, and 1.4 acres respectively in Nabdam District (Table 2.12). It is worth noting the large standard deviations of both HH farms and individual men's farms in both districts. That indicates that some cultivate large farms while others have small farms. In the case of women, the farm areas are relatively small, and the variations are also small.

Table 2.12: Household and individual farm sizes (in acres)

		Household (HH) farms (A)	Individual men farms (B)	Individual women's farms (C)	Household farm holding (A+B+C)
Central Gonja	Average area	17.2	9.7	3.2	30.1
	Std. Dev.	20.9	16.6	1.5	18.2
	Max	60	65	5	-
	Min	1	1	2	-
Nabdam	Average area	4.6	1.6	1.3	7.5
	Std. Dev.	4.2	1.1	0.6	3.9
	Max	25	4	2	-
	Min	1	1	1	-
Total (both Districts)	Average area	9.5	6.9	2.6	8.1
	Std. Dev.	14.7	13.9	1.5	13.7
	Max	60	65	5	65
	Min	1	1	1	1

Source: Field survey, April 2023.

Figure 2.2: Distribution of household (HH), individual men and individual women farm sizes

2.3.2 Methods of land acquisition for farming

Table 2.13 shows that all the farmers surveyed in the Central Gonja District acquired their farmlands through inheritance. In the case of Nabdam District, about 93.5% of the land for HH farms was through inheritance. Only 33.3% of individual women farm plots were obtained through inheritance. Land for farming can be obtained through lease, rented, or borrowed in Nabdam District (Table 2.13). Customary land tenure is the accepted tenure system in both districts and under land ownership is generally communal with varied rules and regulations. Women, however, do not normally inherit land except in special cases.

2.3.3 Land preparation methods

The relative use of different types of land preparation methods on the three types of farms during the 2022 cropping season in the districts is presented in Table 2.14. The commonest method of land preparation in Central Gonja District is the use of a tractor. Overall, over 70% of farm plots in the district were prepared for planting using tractors in the 2022 season. It is noteworthy that over 80% of the women plots were prepared using tractors. The other main land preparation method in the Central Gonja District is the use of hoes. That was used on only the HH and individual men plots. The women do not use it because it is a tedious and energy - sapping method. Figure 2.3 clearly shows that in terms of percentage, women in Central Gonja use considerable weedicides in land preparation eventhough it is lower than the use of tractors and hoes.

Table 2.13: Methods of land acquisition for farming

District	Method of land acquisition	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja	Inheritance	20	100.0	15	100.0	6	100.0	41	100.0
	Total	20	100.0	15	100.0	6	100.0	41	100.0
Nabdam	Inheritance	29	93.5	7	87.5	1	33.3	37	88.1
	Leased	-	-	-	-	2	66.7	2	4.8
	Rented	1	3.2	1	12.5	-	-	2	4.8
	Borrowed (Free)	1	3.2	-	-	-	-	1	2.4
	Total	31	100.0	8	100.0	3	100.0	42	100.0
Total (both Districts)	Inheritance	49	96.1	22	95.7	7	77.8	78	94.0
	Leased	-	-	-	-	2	22.2	2	2.4
	Rented	1	2.0	1	4.3	-	-	2	2.4
	Borrowed (Free)	1	2.0	-	-	-	-	1	1.2
	Total	51	100.0	23	100.0	9	100.0	83	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 2.14: Methods for land preparation

District	Method of land preparation	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja	Tractor	14	70.0	10	66.7	5	83.3	29	70.7
	Hoe	5	25.0	4	26.7	-	-	9	22.0
	Weedicides	1	5.0	1	6.7	1	16.7	3	7.3
	Bullock/ donkey	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	No -till (at the beginning)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total	20	100.0	15	100.0	6	100.0	41	100.0
Nabdam	Tractor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Hoe	14	45.2	2	25.0	1	33.3	17	40.5
	Weedicides	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Bullock/donkey	17	54.8	6	75.0	2	66.7	25	59.5
	No -till	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total	31	100.0	8	100.0	3	100.0	42	100.0
Total (both Districts)	Tractor	14	25.5	10	43.5	5	55.6	29	33.3
	Hoe	19	34.5	6	26.1	1	11.1	26	29.9
	Weedicides	5	9.1	1	4.3	1	11.1	7	8.0
	Bullock/donkey	17	30.9	6	26.1	2	22.2	25	28.7
	No- till	-	-	-	-	-	--	-	-
	Total	55	100.0	23	100.0	9	100.0	87	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Figure 2.3: Percentage of land preparation type used in different farm plot types

In contrast, the use of bullock/donkey plough and hoe are the common means of land preparation in the Nabdam District, 59.5% and 40.5% respectively. Tractors and weedicides are not used at all, according to this survey. That may not be exactly so, but their use is definitely very low. Tractors are hardly used because of the small farm sizes, and weedicides are also rarely used because of cost and also because of significant sensitization by several NGOs on the dangers of their use. The increasing cost of land preparation by bullock/donkey plough and hoe can however cause the use of weedicides for land preparation to increase. There is a need for constant sensitization against their use. Farmers are very conscious of the comparative costs of land preparation, the most difficult of all their farm activities. In terms of percentage use of the different land preparation methods in the Nabdam District, the bullock/donkey plough is used more in individual men and women farms than in HH farms (Table 2.12 and Figure 2.3). That is understandable since HH farms are usually attended to first and by all family members. Also, HH farms are mainly compound farms that have been cultivated over several years, even decades, so land preparation is less difficult.

2.3.4 Numbers of farm plots and their locations

As given in Table 2.15 a household holding (all farm plots in the HH) in Central Gonja District has an average of as many as 41 farm plots while that in Nabdam District has an average of only 11. HH farm plots are the majority in Central Gonja (average of 20) but in Nabdam the individual men plots are the largest (average of 6) (Table 2.15). It is to be noted that the numbers of plots do not necessarily reflect the total farm sizes since a farm plot is a distinctly contiguous area of land in which particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of

the size. In both districts, women have the lowest average number of farm plots (6 in Central Gonja and 3 in Nabdam).

Table 2.15: Numbers of farm plots¹ per HH, locations, and walking time to farms

	Farm Plot category	Compound farm		Bush farm		Number of farm plots	Average time spent to travel from home to the bush farms	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq		Mean distance (minutes)	Standard deviation
Central Gonja	HH farm plots	0	0	20	100	20	37.4	25.8
	Individual men farm plots	0	0	15	100	15	30.7	25.0
	Individual women farm plots	0	0	6	100	6	16.2	9.3
	Total	0	0	41	100	41	31.8	24.5
Nabdam	HH farm plots	28	90.3	3	9.7	31	8.8	21.8
	Individual men farm plots	2	25.0	6	75.0	8	61.4	63.3
	Individual women farm plots	1	33.3	2	66.7	3	46.7	42.5
	Total	31	73.8	11	26.2	42	21.5	40.0
Total (both Districts)	HH farm plots	28	54.9	23	45.1	51	20.0	27.2
	Individual men farm plots	2	8.7	21	91.3	23	41.3	43.6
	Individual women farm plots	1	11.1	8	88.3	9	26.3	27.2
	Total	31	37.3	52	62.7	83	26.6	33.5

Source: Field survey, April 2023

As explained earlier, farmers in the Central Gonja District do not have “compound farms”. All their farms are “bush farms” since they are located some distance from homesteads (see Table 2.15). It takes, on average, 32 minutes to walk to their farms from their homes, and the farthest is the HH farms (walking time of 37 minutes) (Table 2.15). The majority of the plots (about 90%) in the Nabdam District are compound farms, that is farms around homesteads (Table 2.15). The distances to women “bush farms” are the shortest for security reasons and also because women, who are involved in most household chores in the mornings and evenings, must spend less time on their farms because of these other activities.

¹ A farm plot refers to a distinctly contiguous area of land in which particular crop or crop mixtures are cultivated irrespective of the size of the area cultivated.

2.4 Fertility of Farmlands and Use of Inorganic and Organic Fertilizers in Farming

2.4.1 Fertility of household and individual farm plots

Farmers' perceived levels of soil fertility of their households and individual farms are presented in Table 2.16. On average, most of the farmers in Central Gonja District (about 61.0%) indicated that their farms were averagely fertile and required external inputs and manure every year. This is followed by 29.3% of farmers who indicated that their soils were fertile but still needed external inputs and manure. None of the farmers in the Central Gonja District perceived that their farms were very fertile. Also, about 9.8% of the farmers perceived their farms to be of poor fertility.

Table 2.16: Perceptions of the fertility of soil on household and individual farm plots

District	Perceived fertility of the soil of different plots	HH farm plots		Individual men farm plots		Individual women farm plots		Total	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	5	25.0	6	40.0	1	16.7	12	29.3
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	13	65.0	8	53.3	4	66.7	25	61.0
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	2	10.0	1	6.7	1	16.7	4	9.8
	Total	20	100.0	15	100.0	6	100.0	41	100.0
Nabdram	Very fertile (does not require manure or external inputs)	2	6.7	3	37.5	1	33.3	6	14.6
	Fertile (but requires some external inputs and manure)	12	40.0	4	50.0	1	33.3	17	41.5
	Average (requires external inputs or manure every year)	16	53.3	1	12.5	1	33.3	18	43.9
	Poor (cannot produce anything without manure and/or external inputs)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Total	30	100.0	8	100.0	3	100.0	41	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In the case of Nabdam District, 43.9% of the farmers perceived their farms to be averagely fertile and requiring external inputs and manure every year while 41.5% of them felt their farms were fertile but they still needed external inputs and manure. Surprisingly, 14.6% perceived their soils to be very fertile and none of them perceived their soils to be of poor fertility (Table 2.16). It is interesting to find out why an area (i.e. Nabdam District) where there has been continuous cultivation on the same lands over decades are perceived to be more fertile, while areas that have large tracts of land (Central Gonja District) where land rotation and even shifting cultivation is possible are perceived less fertile.

2.4.2 Use of inorganic fertilizers

Some farmers in both districts (60.0% in Central Gonja and 48.4% in Nabdam) applied inorganic fertilizers to their crops while others did not (Table 2.17). Overall, less than 50% of the farmers applied inorganic fertilizers. In Central Gonja District, inorganic fertilizers were applied to about 60% of HH farms and 33% to individual men farms. No fertilizer was applied to the individual women farm plots. The usual reason for the case of women is that they cannot afford to buy fertilizers. In the case of Nabdam, the distribution of those who apply fertilizers and those who do not is about 50/50 (Table 2.17). However, few women apply fertilizer to their farm plots. It should be noted that the use of inorganic fertilizer depends on the type of crops grown on the farm plots. Typically, inorganic fertilizers are used for cereal crops, particularly maize. All farmers say that the varieties of maize they plant cannot yield much without the use of inorganic fertilizers. The use of inorganic fertilizers for legumes (groundnuts and beans) is very limited. That partly explains the relatively low use of inorganic fertilizers by women farmers. Most of them tend to cultivate leguminous crops.

Table 2.17: Inorganic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	12	60.0	8	40.0	15	48.4	16	51.6
Individual men farm plots	5	33.3	10	66.7	4	50.0	4	50.0
Individual women farm plots	0	0.0	6	100.0	1	33.3	2	66.7
Total	17	41.5	24	58.5	20	47.6	22	52.4

Source: Field survey, April 2023

A majority of the farmers (over 70%) who apply inorganic fertilizers believe the fertilizer are effective and do increase their yields (Table 2.18). It is however worth noting that overall, over 30% said the use of fertilizers resulted in a negative response, especially in the case of individual women farms² in Nabdam District. Some women farm plots in Nabdam District may be so degraded or acidic that there is hardly any response to inorganic fertilizer use. Some of the farmers also indicate that the legumes they cultivate (groundnuts and beans) respond marginally, if at all, to inorganic fertilizer application.

² The very few women responses (6 in Central Gonja and 3 in Nabdam) in the case of the individual women farm plots makes it necessary for one to be cautious in drawing conclusions.

Table 2.18: Farmers' perceived crops response to inorganic fertilizers

Farm Plot Category	Central Gonja District				Nabdam District			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	14	73.7	5	26.3	26	83.9	5	16.1
Individual men farm plots	11	73.3	4	26.7	5	62.5	3	37.5
Individual women farm plots	4	66.7	2	33.3	1	33.3	2	66.7
Total	29	72.5	11	27.5	32	76.2	10	23.8

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The quantities of inorganic fertilizer used (in kilograms) across the various farm plots are indicated in Table 2.19. The average quantities used are 174.7 kg/acre in Central Gonja District and 135 kg/acre in Nabdam District. The use in individual men farm plots is higher than in the household farm plots in both districts. The standard deviations are also lower for the case of individual men farm plots than for HH farm plots. That shows the greater attention men farmers tend to give to their individual farm plots with regard to soil fertility management of their plots.

Table 2.19: Fertilizer use per acre (kg/acre) in 2022 cropping season

		Household HH farm plots	Individual men farm plots	Individual women farm plots	Household farm holding
Central Gonja	Average	168.3	190.0	-	174.7
	Std. Dev.	102.4	89.4	-	96.5
	Max	400	300	-	400
	Min	20	100	-	20
Nabdam	Average	123.3	187.5	100 (1 plot)	135.0
	Std. Dev.	117.1	94.6	-	110.7
	Max	450	250	100	450
	Min	25	50	100	25
Total (both Districts)	Average area	143.3	188.9	100	153.2
	Std. Dev.	111.1	85.8	-	104.9
	Max	450	300	100	450
	Min	20	50	100	20

Source: Field survey, April 2023

2.4.3 Use of organic fertilizers

Table 2.20 shows that there is a very wide difference between the use of organic fertilizer/manure in Central Gonja Districts and Nabdam District. While organic fertilizer is hardly used in Central Gonja (about 7.3% of plots), the percentage number of plots to which organic fertilizer was applied in Nabdam District was 88.1% (Table 2.20). There is a need for extensive sensitization of the importance of organic fertilizer production and use in the Central Gonja District. The organic fertilizer use in Nabdam is highest (93.5%) for HH farm plots, followed by individual men farm plots (87.5%), and relatively low for individual women farm

plots (33.3%). That is again expected since women generally have limited access to animal manure. Women need to be exposed to composting so that they can produce some organic fertilizer for their farms.

Table 2.20: Organic fertilizer utilization

Farm Plots	Central Gonja District				Nabdam District			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
HH farm plots	1	5.0	19	95.0	29	93.5	2	6.5
Individual men farm plots	1	6.7	14	93.3	7	87.5	1	12.5
Individual women farm plots	1	16.7	5	93.3	1	33.3	2	66.7
Total	3	7.3	38	92.7	37	88.1	5	11.9

Source: Field survey, April 2023

CHAPTER 3

FARMING SYSTEMS BY DISTRICTS

3.1 Crop-Based Systems

3.1.1 Crops/crop mixtures

From the survey, households had varied crops and crop mixtures grown on farm plots. The variation in crops/crop mixtures depends on factors such as geographical location, climate, culture, and individual preferences. Tables 3.1 and 3.2 present the different crop mixtures in HH farms (as given by HHHs) and in individual women farms (as given by WiHHs) in Central Gonja District. The most common mixture is maize/groundnut/cassava in HH farms and maize/groundnut in individual women farms Central Gonja. It can be observed that the crop mixtures in the Central Gonja District are largely cereal/legume/root.

Table 3.1: Crop mixtures in HH farm plots - Central Gonja District

Crop/Crop Mixtures	Frequency*	% Frq.
Maize/Groundnut/Cassava	4	22.2
Rice/Maize/Groundnut/Cassava	3	16.7
Maize/Yam/Cassava	2	11.1
Rice/Maize/Groundnut	2	11.1
Maize/ Groundnut	2	11.1
Rice/Maize/Cashew	1	5.6
Maize/Groundnut/Yam/Cassava	1	5.6
Millet/ Maize/Groundnut/ Yam	1	5.6
Maize/ Bambara groundnut/Yam	1	5.6
Rice/Maize/Yam/ Cashew	1	5.6
Total	18	100.0

*It is necessary to be cautious with results from very few responses.

Source: Field survey, May 2023

Table 3.2: Individual women plots – WiHH Central Gonja District

Crop/Crop Mixtures	Frequency	% Frequency
Groundnut	9	40.9
Groundnut/Okro	5	22.7
Maize/Groundnut	3	13.6
Groundnut/Soybeans	2	9.1
Maize/Groundnut/Okro	1	4.5
Maize/Groundnut/Neri/Soybeans	1	4.5
Groundnut/Neri/Soybeans	1	4.5
Total	22	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In the Nabdam District, the mixtures are largely cereal/legume/vegetables as given in Table 3.3 for HH farms (HHHs) and Table 3.4 for individual women farms (WiHHs). It is clear that the farming systems in Central Gonja and Nabdam are quite different even in types of crops cultivated and their combinations. That is partly because of the differences in land sizes and availability of farm lands. Main crops commonly grown by men also tend to differ from those grown by women in their individual farms.

Table 3.3: Crop mixtures in HH farm plots – Nabdam District

Crop/Crop Mixtures	Frequency	% Frequency
Millet/ Sorghum/ Rice/ Maize/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)	3	17.6
Millet/ Maize/ Groundnut	2	11.8
Millet/ Sorghum/ Maize	2	11.8
Millet/ Maize/ Groundnut/ Bambara groundnut	2	11.8
Millet/ Sorghum/ Rice/ Maize/ Groundnut	2	11.8
Millet/ Maize/ Bambara groundnut	2	11.8
Maize/ Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)/ Soybeans	1	5.9
Millet/ Sorghum/ Groundnut/ Bambara groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)/ Soybeans/ Sweet potato/ Frafra potato (Pesa)/ Leafy vegetables (local)/ Pepper/ Tomatoes/ Okro/ Mango/ Cashew	1	5.9
Millet/ Maize/ Groundnut/ Bambara groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)/ Soybeans	1	5.9
Millet/ Rice/ Maize/ Groundnut	1	5.9
Total	17	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 3.4: Individual women farm plots – WiHH Nabdam District

Crop/Crop Mixtures	Frequency	% Frequency
Rice	4	40.0
Rice/ Groundnut	2	20.0
Groundnut	1	10.0
Millet/ Maize/ Groundnut	1	10.0
Maize/ Soybeans	1	10.0
Groundnut/ Beans (Cowpea)	1	10.0
Total	10	100.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Given the complexities in the crop mixtures, it is necessary to determine the relative importance of crops to both men and women in the households. Both quantitative and qualitative methods have been used to get a holistic picture of what crops the farmers regard as most important to them. The first method is computing (collating) the numbers of plots the crops appear as sole or in mixtures using the ten most common crops/crop mixtures in each of the districts (i.e.

Tables 3.1 to 3.4). The results obtained are as given in Tables 3.5 and 3.6 for Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts respectively. The results in Table 3.5 show that maize, groundnut, cassava, rice, and yam are the five most important crops grown by Central Gonja men, and groundnut, okro and maize are the top most crops cultivated by women in the district.

In the Nabdam District, millet, maize, groundnuts and sorghum top the list of important crops for men, and rice, groundnut and maize are the most important crops for the women. Groundnut and maize feature prominently in both districts and for men and women.

Table 3.5: Relative importance of crops to men and women in Central Gonja District using crop/crop mixtures indicated in Table 3.1 and 3.2.

Central Gonja (HH farms plots)			Central Gonja (Individual women plots)		
Crops	Freq.	% Freq.	Crops	Freq.	% Freq.
Maize	18	30.5	Groundnut	22	59.5
Groundnut	14	23.7	Okro	6	16.2
Cassava	10	16.9	Maize	5	13.5
Rice	7	11.9	Soybean	2	5.4
Yam	6	10.2	Neri	2	5.4
Cashew	2	3.4	Total	37	100.0
Millet	1	1.7			
Bambara groundnut	1	1.7			
Total	59	100.0			

Source: Field survey, April 2023.

Table 3.6: Relative importance of crops to men and women in Nabdam District using crop/crop mixtures indicated in Table 3.3 and 3.4.

Nabdam (HH farm plots)			Nabdam (Individual women plots)		
Crops	Freq.	% Freq.	Crops	Freq.	% Freq.
Millet	16	20.0	Rice	6	40.0
Maize	16	20.0	Groundnut	5	33.3
Groundnut	15	18.8	Maize	2	13.3
Sorghum	8	10.0	Beans (cowpea)	1	6.7
Beans (cowpea)	6	7.5	Soybean	1	6.7
Bambara groundnut	6	7.5	Total	15	100.0
Rice	6	7.5			
Soybeans	3	3.8			
Tomatoes	1	1.3			
Pepper	1	1.3			
Sweet potato	1	1.3			
Okro	1	1.3			
Total	80	100.0			

Source: Field survey, April 2023.

For the purpose of robustness and triangulation a qualitative method was used in addition to rank crops according to their importance to men and women in the households. HHHs and WiHHs were asked to rank crops cultivated in order of importance to them on a scale of 1 to 5, 1 being the most important and 5 the least. A method of **weighted scores of ranked frequencies³ (WSRF)** was used. The method makes rankings more robust. Many socio-economic and other factors are involved in rankings (perceptions) and the factors and their levels (magnitudes) differ from person to person. There is need to be more robust in methodology to obtain the correct composite of perceptions. Figure 3.1 presents the relative importance of crops to men in the survey area using the method. HHHs in the Central Gonja District ranked groundnut, maize, yam, cassava, and soybean as the five most important crops while in the Nabdam District, they ranked millet, maize, sorghum, rice and groundnuts as the five most important crops. Maize appears very important in both districts because it is a cash crop and gradually becoming a staple. Maize is widely promoted by projects and government agencies and the climatic and soil conditions also favour its production in both districts. Vegetables such as pepper, tomatoes, and okra were generally ranked low in terms of their importance.

Figure 3.1 Relative importance of crops according to HHHs (men)

In the case of WiHHs (women), the important crops for the Central Gonja District were groundnut, maize, okro, soybean, and cassava while in the Nabdam District they ranked millet, maize, sorghum, rice, and groundnuts as most important (Figure 3.2). It is interesting to note that the ranking from the women was similar to the men except for okro. Okro which is ranked low by men is considered the third most important by women in the Central Gonja District.

³ See Appendix 1 for details of the method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies (WSRF).

The quantitative and qualitative methods agree to large extent on the crops considered most important to men and women in the districts even though some differences can be observed. For example in Central Gonja the qualitative method scores groundnut higher than maize, which is not so in the quantitative case. It will be interesting to note the several differences and to use them in discussions with the people.

Figure 3.2: Relative Importance of crops according to WiHHs (women)

3.1.2 Planting materials and sources

Though the types of planting materials and sources of acquisition can vary from person to person, the results from the survey show that most farmers from both districts use indigenous seeds from their storages. Tables 3.7 and 3.8 present the results of the types and sources of planting materials in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts respectively. Respondents were also asked to list the special characteristics of the planting materials that they use. The most frequent characteristic from each district was “high yielding” varieties. Thus, most households use high -yielding indigenous seeds that are readily available to them from their own storages.

Table 3.7: Types and sources of planting materials- Central Gonja District

Type of seeds used		Source of seed							
		Own seed		Local seed (purchased)		Local seed (from other farmers)		Improved seed (purchased)	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	9	75.0	0	0.0	3	25.0	0	0.0
	Improved (Open - pollinated)	0	0.0	2	28.6	0	0.0	5	71.4
	Indigenous	3	60.0	1	20.0	0	0.0	1	20.0
Rice	Improved	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
	Indigenous	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Indigenous	13	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Ground-nut	Improved	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
	Indigenous	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Indigenous	2	66.7	1	33.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Soybeans	Improved	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0
	Indigenous	7	87.5	1	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Indigenous	10	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 3.8: Types and sources of planting materials- Nabdam District

Type of seeds used		Own seed		Local seed (purchased)		Local seed (from other farmers)		Improved seed (purchased)	
		Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Maize	Indigenous (local)	16	88.89	2	11.1	0	0.0	0	0
	Improved (Open-pollinated)	0	0.0	3	75.0	0	0.0	1	25.0
Rice	Rice – Indigenous	11	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sorghum	Indigenous	15	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	“Improved”	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Millet	Indigenous	24	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Groundnut	Indigenous	10	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	“Improved”	0	0.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	1	50.0
Beans (Cowpea)	Indigenous	5	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	“Improved”						0.0		0.0
Soybeans	Indigenous	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	“Improved”	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Sweet potato	Indigenous (local)	2	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Vegetables	Indigenous (local)	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

3.1.4 Crop production constraints

Crop production can face various constraints that impact agricultural productivity. These constraints may differ by gender, region, or agroecological zone. Respondents were asked to rank their crop production constraints on a scale of 1 to 5 similar to what was done for most important crops (section 3.1.1). The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies (WSRF) was used to determine the relative importance of the constraints to the respondents. In the Central Gonja District, the first three most significant constraints are soil fertility, finance, and erratic rainfall. For the Nabdam District, pests and diseases, soil fertility, and small farm sizes were the main constraints (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3 HHHs (men) crop production constraints by District

In Central Gonja, findings from the focus group discussions and key informant interviews with men confirmed the presence of soil infertility, irregular rain patterns, weed infestation, pests and diseases, financial constraints, and limited access to production inputs, especially fertilizers and seeds. In a focus group discussion with men, it was affirmed that pests and diseases, soil infertility, late planting due to funerals, weed infestation, delayed rainfall, inadequate labor, and limited access to production inputs are prevalent issues. These challenges were further substantiated by key informant interviews, emphasizing them as constraints on crop production in the Nabdam District.

For the women, erratic rainfall, soil fertility, and access to production inputs are the main crop production constraints in the Central Gonja District. For the Nabdam District, the main crop production constraints are related to soil fertility, erratic rainfall, and finance (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4 WiHH crop production constraints by District

The findings from the focus group discussions for women confirm the existence of several constraints hampering crop production in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. Participants in both districts consistently highlighted issues such as poor rainfall, low soil fertility, lack of finance, weed management, pests and diseases, and the inability to access fertilizer (production input access).

It is worth noting that in Ghana, there are no marked differences in crop production constraints at the district level and also by gender with soil fertility, erratic rainfall, and finance running through them all.

3.2 Livestock-Based Systems

3.2.1 Animal ownership and management

Livestock-based systems play a crucial role in sustaining rural livelihoods and ensuring food security in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. Understanding the dynamics of animal ownership and management by gender in specific districts is essential for informed agricultural development. Tables 3.9, 3.10, 3.11, and 3.12 provide distinct practices of animal ownership and management in the Central Gonja and Nabdam districts, with a focus on men (household heads) and women.

In the Central Gonja District, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, and poultry consisting of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.9)

Table 3.9: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Central Gonja District for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	9.5	7.5	-	-	2.7	2.3	-	-
Sheep	7.6	4.3	-	-	9.6	7.6	-	-
Goats	6.6	2.9	-	-	6.7	4.2	-	-
Fowls (Chickens)	11.0	3.4	-	-	11.5	4.2	-	-
Guinea fowls	3.0	-	-	-	4.0	3.6	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 10, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 8. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 3, with an SD of 2. Sheep ownership averaged 8 in 2022, with a standard deviation of 4.3, while goats averaged 7. In 2023, sheep ownership increased to 10, while goat ownership remained constant. Fowl and guinea fowl ownership averaged 11 and 3, respectively, in 2022. In 2023, fowl ownership increased to 12, and guinea fowl ownership rose to 4. The decrease in cattle ownership coincided with an increase in sheep ownership, suggesting a shift to smaller livestock in Central Gonja District. The consistent or increased ownership of fowls and guinea fowls points to stability or growth in poultry farming, possibly due to their faster income generation.

Women owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, and fowls (chickens) (Table 3.10).

Table 3.10: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Central Gonja District for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	10.00		1.00		11.00		11.00	
Sheep	3.00	1.41	50.00	707.00	4.00	2.83		
Goats	3.50	1.31	38.00	1.06	6.25	4.98	0.38	0.74
Fowls (Chickens)	10.60	5.32	2.00	2.74	15.40	8.14	1.20	1.30

Note: It is difficult to understand the highlighted numbers. If the responses are correct then the respondents must have been livestock traders.

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by women was 10, with an average sale of around 1. By 2023, the average cattle ownership slightly increased to 11, with an average sale of 11. Among women in the Central Gonja, sheep ownership averaged 3 in 2022, with a standard deviation

(SD) of 1.4, while goats averaged 4, with an SD of 1.3. In 2023, sheep ownership increased to 4, while goat ownership rose to 6. Fowl (chicken) ownership averaged 11 in 2022. In 2023, fowl ownership increased to 15. The average number of fowls (chickens) sold in 2022 and 2023 was 2 and 1, respectively.

There are distinct patterns in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the Central Gonja District. Both men and women own various types of livestock, including cattle, small ruminants, and poultry. Women showed a slight increase in cattle ownership from 2022 to 2023, with a notable rise in cattle sales. Additionally, there was an increase in women's ownership of sheep, goats, and fowls from 2022 to 2023.

In the Nabdam District, men owned various types of livestock in 2022 and 2023, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, pigs, and poultry consisting of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.11).

Table 3.11: Men livestock ownership and sales in the Nabdam District for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	3.1	1.6	-	-	2.4	1.8	-	-
Sheep	4.6	2.1	-	-	3.4	2.4	-	-
Goats	5.2	1.9	-	-	4.3	2.8	-	-
Pigs	60.0	-	-	-	20	-	-	-
Fowls (Chickens)	13.5	7.7	-	-	7.00	5.60	-	-
Guinea fowls	13.2	5.6	-	-	8.00	5.50	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In 2022, the average cattle ownership by men was 3, with a standard deviation (SD) of around 2. By 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 2, with an SD of 2. Sheep ownership averaged 5 in 2022, with a standard deviation of 2.1, while goats also averaged 5. In 2023, sheep ownership declined to 3, and goat ownership also decreased to 4. Fowl and guinea fowl ownership averaged 14 and 13, respectively, in 2022. However, in 2023, fowl ownership increased to 7, while guinea fowl ownership declined to 8. The reduction in cattle ownership, accompanied by declines in sheep and goat numbers, suggests a potential shift in the favored livestock species among the men in Nabdam District. This change might stem from diverse factors like economic considerations or shifts in farming methods. Similarly, the decrease in guinea fowl ownership, contrasted with the rise in fowl ownership, hints at a possible evolution within the poultry industry.

In 2022 and 2023, women owned various types of livestock, including large ruminants such as cattle, small ruminants like sheep and goats, and poultry such as fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls (Table 3.12).

Table 3.12: Women livestock ownership and sales in the Nabdam District for the years 2022 and 2023

Types of animals	Number owned in 2022		Number sold in 2022		Number owned in 2023		Number sold in 2023	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Cattle	15.0	18.39	9.0	12.73	3.5	2.12	-	-
Sheep	4.7	3.25	1.5	2.25	3.0	2.42	0.14	0.54
Goats	5.2	2.20	2.0	2.47	3.5	2.32	0.5	1.50
Fowls (Chickens)	8.6	4.89	3.4	4.48	5.9	7.46	0.9	1.22
Guinea fowls	12.0	4.45	3.8	4.49	9.8	9.78	0.6	1.54

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In 2022, women in the Nabdam District had an average cattle ownership of 15, with an average sale of 9. However, by 2023, the average cattle ownership declined to 4. Among Nabdam women, sheep ownership averaged 5 in 2022, with an average sale of 2, while goats averaged 5, with an average sale of 4. In 2023, sheep ownership decreased to 3, and goat ownership declined to 4. However, the average sales for sheep and goats in 2023 were 0.14 and 0.53, respectively. Fowl (chicken) and guinea fowl ownership averaged 9 and 12 in 2022, with average sales of 3 and 4, respectively. In 2023, fowl and guinea fowl ownership decreased to 6 and 10, respectively. The average number of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls sold in 2022 were 3 and 4, respectively. In 2023, the average number of fowls (chickens) and guinea fowls sold was 0.9 and 0.6, respectively.

Clear patterns emerge in livestock ownership and management practices between men and women in the Nabdam District. Both genders experienced changes in livestock ownership: men exhibited a decrease in cattle ownership and a noticeable shift in poultry, while women saw declines in cattle, sheep, and goat ownership, coupled with reduced poultry ownership and sales. The factors driving these changes could include economic factors or other dynamic elements within the Nabdam District.

The Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts exhibit significant differences in livestock ownership and management between men and women. In Central Gonja, both men and women own various types of livestock. Men experienced a decline in cattle ownership, while women showed a slight increase. Women in Central Gonja also demonstrated increases in sheep, goat, and fowl ownership from 2022 to 2023. In contrast, in the Nabdam District, men displayed decreased ownership of cattle, sheep, and goats, potentially indicating a shift in favored livestock species. Women in Nabdam also witnessed reductions in sheep, goat, and fowl ownership along with decreased sales from 2022 to 2023. These variations suggest distinct

trends in livestock management practices between the two districts, possibly influenced by economic considerations or changes in farming practices.

3.2.2 Animal breeds, sources, and characteristics

Animal breeds

Animal breeds may vary based on geographical locations and gender-specific practices. Table 2.30 shows the different types of breeds reared in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. The livestock breeds commonly reared by men in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts are indigenous or local breeds (Table 3.10). The commonly reared indigenous livestock breeds in Central Gonja and Nabdam do not differ. They include sheep, goats, fowl (chickens), and cattle (Table 3.13).

Table 3.13: Livestock breeds reared by men in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts

Livestock	Commonly reared breeds	Central Gonja		Nabdam	
		Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cattle	Indigenous (local)	4.00	16.00	9.00	12.33
Sheep	Indigenous	6.00	24.00	17.00	23.29
Goats	Indigenous	6.00	24.00	22.00	30.14
Fowls (Chickens)	Indigenous	6.00	24.00	12.00	16.44
Guinea fowls	Indigenous	2.00	8.00	11.00	15.07
Ducks	Indigenous	1.00	4.00	-	-
Donkeys	Indigenous	-	-	1.00	1.37
Guinea Pigs	Indigenous	-	-	1.00	1.37

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Sources of Animal Breeds

The main source from which the animals are obtained varies based on the type of animal (Tables 3.14 and 3.15). In the Central Gonja District, Table 3.14 shows that most cattle (75%) and sheep (50%) breeds are purchased locally.

Table 3.11: Men main source of animal breeds in Central Gonja District

Animal	Local - given by other farmers		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Cattle	0	0	3	75	1	25
Ducks	0	0	1	100	0	0
Fowls (chickens)	0	0	3	50	3	50
Goats	1	16.7	2	33.3	3	50
Guinea fowls	0	0	1	50	1	50
Sheep	1	16.7	3	50	2	33.3

Source: Field survey, April 2023

From Table 3.14, only a few of the cattle (25%) and sheep (33%) breeds source are owned by male farmers. Most of the indigenous goat breeds (50%) are owned by farmers, while 33% and 17% are purchased locally and given by other farmers, respectively. For both fowls and guinea fowls, half of the indigenous breeds are owned by farmers, while the other half is purchased locally. In the Nabdam District, Table 3.15 indicates that all indigenous breeds of fowls (chickens), guinea fowls, and goats are owned by farmers.

Table 3.15: Men main source of animal breeds in Nabdam District

Animal	Exotic- purchased		Local – purchased		Own breed	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Cattle	1	11.1	1	11.1	7	77.8
Donkeys	0	0	0	0	1	100
Fowls (chickens)	0	0	0	0	12	100
Goats	0	0	0	0	22	100
Guinea fowls	0	0	0	0	11	100
Guinea pigs	0	0	0	0	1	100
Sheep	0	0	3	17.6	14	82.4

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The majority of cattle (78%) and sheep (82%) breeds are owned by farmers. Only 18% of sheep and 11% of cattle breeds are purchased locally. The differences in livestock breeds and sourcing practices between Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts are multifaceted. The consistent rearing of indigenous or local breeds in both districts suggests a reliance on breeds adapted to the local environment, possibly due to their resilience to local conditions. The variation in sourcing practices, particularly the higher percentage of locally purchased cattle and sheep in Central Gonja compared to Nabdam, may indicate differences in market accessibility or preferences. A higher percentage of locally owned livestock in Nabdam District might indicate a more self-sufficient livestock economy. In contrast, the higher reliance on local purchases in Central Gonja may suggest dependence on external markets.

Special characteristics of animal breeds

Animal breeds exhibit unique traits or features that set one breed apart from another. Tables 3.16 and 3.17 showcase the distinct characteristics of animals for men in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts.

In the Central Gonja District, the majority of male respondents indicated that cattle breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat and milk and are easily available within the district (Table 3.16).

Table 3.16: Special characteristics of animal breeds in Central Gonja District

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg)		Hardy (resilient in the environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cattle	3	42.9	1	14.3	-	-	-	-	3	42.9	-	-
Sheep	5	35.7	1	7.1	1	7.1	2	14.3	5	35.7	-	-
Goats	3	17.6	3	17.6	1	5.9	3	17.8	6	35.3	1	5.9
Fowls (Chickens)	2	14.3	-	-	2	14.3	4	28.6	5	35.7	1	7.1
Guinea fowls	1	20.0	-	-	1	20.0	2	40.0	1	20.0	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The majority of respondents attribute special characteristics to sheep and goats, noting their easy availability, high productivity, and good taste. Specifically for goats, 18% indicate their hardiness and resilience to prevailing environmental conditions. Nearly the same percentage agrees that goat and sheep breeds in Central Gonja District are resistant to diseases. Regarding fowl (chicken) breeds, most respondents highlight their easy availability and good taste. Fowls are also recognized for their disease resistance and high productivity in terms of meat and egg production. Guinea fowl breeds were similarly indicated by the majority to possess traits such as good taste, high productivity, especially in egg production, disease resistance, and easy availability in Central Gonja.

In the Nabdam District, the majority of male respondents indicated that cattle breeds are known for being highly productive in terms of meat and milk (24%), hardy (20%), and producing a lot of manure (20%). Also, cattle breeds were described by 12% each as being easily available, disease resistant, and taste good (Table 3.17).

The majority of respondents attribute special characteristics to sheep and goats, noting their easy availability, hardiness, high productivity, disease resistance, and good taste. They are also mentioned to produce ample manure. Fowls and guinea fowls are recognized for their good taste, easy availability, and high productivity, particularly in egg production in Nabdam.

Table 3.17: Special characteristics of animal breeds in Nabdam District

Animal	Highly productive (meat, milk, egg, etc)		Hardy (resilient in the environment)		Disease resistant		Good taste		Easily available		Produces a lot of manure	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cattle	6	24	5	20	3	12	3	12	3	12	5	20
Sheep	6	13.30	8	17.80	6	13.30	6	13.3	13	28.9	6	13.3
Donkey	0		1	33.33	1	33.33	0		1	33.33	0	
Goats	10	14.7	10	14.7	9	13.2	12	17.6	18	26.5	9	13.2
Fowls (Chickens)	6	17.1	3	8.6	3	8.6	8	22.9	10	28.6	5	14.3
Guinea fowls	6	17.6	4	11.8	2	5.9	11	32.4	8	23.5	3	8.8

Source: Field survey, April 2023

3.2.3 Livestock production constraints

Livestock production encounters diverse constraints that may affect its efficiency, with variations observed across districts, genders, and types of livestock, including large ruminants (e.g., cattle), small ruminants (e.g., goats and sheep), and poultry (e.g., fowls - chickens and guinea fowls). Figures 3.6 to 3.15 illustrate the distinct types of livestock and the constraints experienced by men and women in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies (WSRF) has been used in analysing and presenting all the livestock constraints.

Cattle production constraints

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 show the cattle production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Central Gonja and Nabdam districts. Diseases, theft, and a lack of feed during the dry season are the cattle production constraints among men in both districts (Figure 3.5). Though these constraints, especially disease and theft, are more pressing in Central Gonja, there is consistency in the cattle production constraints among men in both districts. However, there are some constraints peculiar to men in the Nabdam district. These include a lack of water during the dry season, limited access to financing for livestock production, challenges in obtaining information to manage livestock, and difficulties in accessing veterinary services.

Figure 3.5 HHH (men) cattle production constraints by District

For women, cattle production constraints include the lack of feed and water during the dry season, as well as diseases (Figure 3.6). The constraints, especially the lack of feed and water during the dry season, are ranked higher by women in Central Gonja compared to Nabdam. Nonetheless, the results still show consistency in the cattle production constraints reported by women in both districts. Poor housing is a specific constraint related to women in cattle production, particularly in the Nabdam District.

Figure 3.6 Women cattle production constraints by District

While there are common cattle production constraints for men and women in both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts, distinct differences exist in the intensity and nature of specific challenges. This variation may require tailored interventions for sustainable livestock production in each district. Common constraints for men in both districts include diseases, theft, and a lack of feed during the dry season. Women in both districts face similar challenges,

such as the lack of feed and water during the dry season and diseases. Despite some variations in specific constraints' intensity, there is overall consistency in the cattle production challenges reported by both genders in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. Disease and theft issues are more severe for men in Central Gonja, while men in Nabdam District face additional unique constraints. Women in Central Gonja experience a higher intensity of constraints related to the lack of feed and water during the dry season compared to their counterparts in Nabdam District. Poor housing is specifically identified as a constraint for women in cattle production, particularly in the Nabdam District.

Goat production constraints

Figures 3.7 and 3.8 show the goat production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Central Gonja and Nabdam districts. In Central Gonja, men's goat production constraints are related to poor housing, theft, diseases, lack of feed in the dry season, and road kills. In the Nabdam district, men's constraints include diseases, theft, lack of water and feed in the dry season, challenges with accessing livestock management information, and veterinary services (Figure 3.7). Though the constraints for men may be similar in both districts, the priorities differ. Most communities in Central Gonja are located along the main ECOWAS highway to Burkina Faso, hence the reason roadkill is peculiar to Central Gonja.

Figure 3.7 HHH (men) goat production constraints by District

For women in both districts, the constraints are related to theft, diseases, poor housing, and a lack of feed and water (Figure 3.8). In Central Gonja District, theft, diseases, poor housing, and a lack of feed are the main constraints for women in goat production. Whereas in Nabdam, the main constraints for women in goat production include diseases, theft, and a lack of water and feed during the dry season.

Figure 3.8 Women's goat production constraints by District

While common constraints, such as diseases and theft, are shared in goat production for both genders across the two districts, priorities and specific constraints differ. Men and women in both districts face common challenges. ‘Road kills’ is specific to men in Central Gonja, while the absence of poor housing for women in Nabdam and the lack of constraints with water and feed during the dry season for women in Central Gonja highlight distinct variations in constraints between the districts.

Sheep production constraints

Figures 3.9 and 3.10 show the sheep production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Central Gonja and Nabdam districts. In Central Gonja, men's most pressing sheep production constraints are poor housing, diseases, theft, lack of market, and a shortage of feed and water during the dry season. In Nabdam district, the constraints for men are related to diseases, theft, lack of feed and water during the dry season, poor housing, challenges with veterinary services, and limited access to livestock management information (Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9 Household head sheep production constraints by District

For women (Figure 3.10), the most pressing sheep production constraints in Central Gonja are theft, diseases, and a lack of feed during the dry season. In Nabdam, the constraints for women are related to diseases, theft, lack of feed and water during the dry season, poor housing, limited access to livestock management information, and challenges with veterinary services.

Figure 3.10 Women sheep production constraints by District

Poultry production constraints

Fowl (chicken) production constraints

Figures 3.11 and 3.12 show the fowl (chicken) production constraints for household heads (men) and women in the Central Gonja and Nabdam districts, respectively. In Central Gonja, men's most pressing fowl (chickens) production constraints are diseases, poor housing, lack of feed during the dry season, theft, lack of water during the dry season, and a lack of market. In Nabdam district, the constraints for men are the same as in Central Gonja, but diseases are ranked as a major constraint in Nabdam. Limited access to livestock management information, challenges with veterinary services, and financing are unique to men in Nabdam District (Figure 3.11)

Figure 3.11 Household head fowl (chicken) production constraints by District

For women (Figure 3.12), the most pressing fowl (chicken) production constraints in both Central Gonja and Nabdam are diseases, theft, lack of feed and water during the dry season, and poor housing. In Nabdam, diseases, and theft are the leading constraints for women in fowl (chicken) production compared to Central Gonja. Although lack of feed during the dry season and poor housing are constraints in Nabdam, they are more dominant in Central Gonja District. The lack of a market is a unique constraint in Nabdam (Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12 Women fowl (chicken) production constraints by District

From Figures 3.11 and 3.12, men and women in both districts share common constraints, including diseases, theft, and seasonal resource scarcity. Central Gonja men uniquely face a lack of market, while in Nabdam, women encounter this unique constraint. Nabdam men confront additional challenges in fowl (chicken) production, such as limited access to livestock management information, difficulties with veterinary services, and financing. For Nabdam women, major constraints are diseases and theft, while the lack of feed during the dry season and poor housing are more dominant issues for women in Central Gonja.

Guinea fowl production constraints

Figures 3.13 and 3.14 show the guinea fowl production constraints for household heads (men) and women in Central Gonja and Nabdam districts, respectively. In Nabdam district, men's most pressing guinea fowl production constraints are theft, diseases, poor housing, limited access to livestock management information, lack of water during the dry season, financing, lack of feed during the dry season, lack of market, and access to veterinary services. Men in Central Gonja expressed no guinea fowl production constraints.

Figure 3.13 Household head guinea fowl production constraints by in Nabdam District

For women (Figure 3.14), the most pressing guinea fowl production constraints in both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts are diseases and theft. Poor housing is a distinctive constraint for women in Central Gonja, while the lack of feed and water during the dry season and challenges in accessing veterinary services are unique constraints for women in Nabdam (Figure 3.14).

Figure 3.14 Women guinea fowl production constraints by District

While diseases and theft are common constraints in guinea fowl production for both men and women across both districts, the specific constraints and variations differ. Central Gonja men did not express constraints, whereas Nabdam men faced multiple challenges. Women in Central Gonja face the distinctive constraint of poor housing, while women in Nabdam have unique challenges related to the lack of feed and water during the dry season and difficulties in accessing veterinary services. These variations underscore the need for tailored interventions addressing the specific constraints faced by men and women in each district.

3. 3 Irrigation Farming Systems

3.3.1 Irrigation types and crops cultivated

None of the 25 households sampled in the Central Gonja District undertook irrigated agriculture and only two among the 25 sampled in Nabdam District undertook irrigated agriculture. Irrigated agriculture, from surface water sources is, however, carried out in several parts of the Central Gonja District, which is drained by two of Ghana's important rivers, the Black and Black Volta Rivers. Both surface and ground water irrigation are also relatively common practices in the Nabdam District (see for example Dittoh, 2020, Dittoh et. al 2013a, Dittoh et al. 2013b, ILSSI, Obuobi et. al.).

The two irrigation types of the two irrigation households in the Nabdam District were smallholder surface water irrigation (rivers and streams) – bucket and jerry can fetch, and smallholder groundwater irrigation (shallow and deep wells) – bucket and jerry can fetch. These are the most irrigation types common across the Upper East Region of Ghana (Dittoh, 2020), including the Nabdam District. The main types of crops grown on these irrigated sites: are rice, tomatoes, pepper, onions, and exotic vegetables such as lettuce.

3.3.2 Constraints and soil amendments

High costs and poor access to production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc) and water shortages were mentioned as the main constraints faced by irrigators in the Nabdam District. Other constraints to irrigation identified during focus group discussions included the destruction of irrigated crops by livestock (due to lack of or inadequate fencing), lack of good vegetable seeds, pests and diseases, and inadequate water lifting devices such as pumps. Organic matter and organic matter mixed with inorganic manure are used to improve irrigated plots. According to the irrigators inorganic fertilizers without organic matter are not good for irrigated plots.

CHAPTER 4

OUTPUT AND INCOME FROM FARMING SYSTEMS

4.1. Income from Crops (Value of Harvested Crops) and Non-farm Sources

4.1.1 Income from crops, and proportions of quantities for home consumption and for sale

The main sources of income to rural households in most parts of the rural areas of Africa and beyond are small-scale crop farming and livestock production. Other sources of income may include petty trading, the sale of labour, businesses, remittances, artisanship, small-scale mining, the sale of firewood and charcoal and others. The nature of small-scale farming activities in the study area and other places makes it difficult to adequately estimate household income. As seen in Tables 3.1 and 3.2, most plots consist of crop mixtures, ranging from two to as many as six. To comprehensively estimate the income from a plot, the value of all the crops harvested in the plot must be determined. Such information is difficult to obtain from farmers through recall interviews. Attempts were, however, made to obtain some idea of the income earned from arable crop farming, which is the main occupation of most household members in the study area, by estimating the value of two main crops in crop mixture plots. In the case of sole crop plots, the value of the sole crop is estimated. It is the total harvested quantity that is valued. The prices are those the farmers gave at the time of the interviews. This explanation is to indicate that caution is required in drawing conclusions from the results since changes, even small changes, in prices and quantities harvested can give drastically different results. Also, what is presented in each case is gross income and not gross margin. Cost of production was not estimated because such information from recall by small farmers is not reliable and will not serve much purpose in this study. Income from livestock production was also not estimated for the same reason of unreliability of the information given by farmers. Table 4.1 gives the procedure and formula used for the estimation of household crop income.

Table 4.1: Method of estimation of household income of harvested crops

Plot	Crops (two most prominent crops in mixtures)		Total quantity harvested (in local units)		Price per unit (local currency)		Value of output (local currency)
	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	
1	A1	B1	Q _{A1}	Q _{B1}	P _{A1}	P _{B1}	$(Q_{A1} \times P_{A1}) + (Q_{B1} \times P_{B1})$
2.	A2	B2	Q _{A2}	Q _{B2}	P _{A2}	P _{B2}	$(Q_{A2} \times P_{A2}) + (Q_{B2} \times P_{B2})$
etc	A _i	B _i	Q _{A_i}	Q _{B_i}	P _{A_i}	P _{B_i}	$(Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i})$
Equation for computation of the estimated household income from harvested crops (where n = number of household plots)							$N \sum_{i=1} ((Q_{A_i} \times P_{A_i}) + (Q_{B_i} \times P_{B_i}))$
A1 = crop A from plot 1; Q _{A1} = A1 harvested quantity; P _{A1} = Price of A1 B1 = crop B from plot 1; Q _{B1} = B1 harvested quantity; P _{B1} = Price of B1 Thus: A _i = Crop A from plot i; Q _{A_i} = A _i harvested quantity; P _{A_i} = Price of A _i etc.							

Table 4.1 gives information on the estimated average annual incomes obtained by households from crops. It should be noted that the value of harvested produce rather than the quantities of crops sold are used in the calculation. On average, households' crop produce was worth about 64,891.50GHC per household per annum in Central Gonja and 7,513.50 GHC in Nabdam. That translate to 3,772.96 GHC per acre per annum for CGD and 1,633.37 per acre per annum for ND. The Nabdam value cannot buy enough fertilizer for an acre of maize or rice. Farmers are thus making huge losses. Any intervention must aim at increasing productivity (output per unit) substantially. There is also need to emphasize on sustainable production to ensure planetary health. That implies agroecological ways of increasing productivity.

Table 4.1: Value of crop output per household and cash income (HHH) (in Ghana Cedis GH¢) -HHH

District	Average income from crops (per Household)		Average income from crops (per acre)		
	Value of harvested crops per HH (HHH) in 2022 (GHC)	Euro equivalent (1 Euro = 11.97GHC)	Average HH farm plot size (acres)	Income per acre (Euros)	Income per acre (in Ghana Cedis)
Central Gonja	64,891.50	5,421.18	17.2	315.18	3,772.76
Nabdam	7,513.50	627.69	4.6	136.45	1,633.37
Both Districts (income per HH)	36,202.5	3,024.44	-	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

4.2 Relative Quantities Normally Allocated for Home Consumption and Sold

Besides selling household produce for income, households in the study area also consume some of their farm produce, as well as share some with relatives and friends among others. Table 4.2 indicates that households in Central Gonja normally allocate about 28% of their farm produce for home consumption (including livestock supplementary feeding and seed), and give out about 7% of the produce to relatives and friends. The women in households in Central Gonja reported relatively low figures, indicating that 16% of produce is usually for home consumption, and 2% is usually given out. The table further explains that relative quantities allocated for home consumption and given out in Nabdam are higher when compared to Central Gonja. The HHH and WiHH in Nabdam respectively reported that 83% and 84% of harvested produce is normally consumed, while 6% and 5% are normally given out. The results from both HHH and WiHH in both districts are consistent since both men and women seemed to have similar perceptions.

The results presented in Table 4.2 depict or confirm the commercialized nature of Central Gonja production, in the sense that most farm produce is traded (about 65%) as compared to what is consumed (28%). On the other hand, farming in Nabdam is more subsistent, such that more of their farm produce is consumed (83%) compared to what is sold (11%). This

computation ignores post-harvest losses because data was not collected on that. There is need to consider special studies on post-harvest losses because they can be substantial and are significant costs to producers,

Table 4.2: Proportions of produce normally reserved for home consumption, given out (as gifts) and sold according men and women in the Zones

Item	Central Gonja District		Nabdam District	
	HHH (men) Mean (Std. Dev.)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std. Dev.)	HHH (men) Mean (Std Dev)	WiHH (women) Mean (Std Dev.)
Proportion (%) normally left for home consumption and other home uses (e.g. livestock, seed etc.) (A)	28 (28)	16 (27)	83 (22)	84 (24)
Proportion (%) quantity normally given out to relatives, friends etc. (as gifts) (B)	7 (20)	2 (3)	6 (6)	5 (8)
Proportion (%) normally sold (100 - (A+B))	65	-	11	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

4.1.2 Income from non-farm sources

Many individuals and households seek additional sources of income beyond their primary occupation of farming. These supplementary income sources can provide financial stability and opportunities for personal or economic growth for the individual and the household. The choice of additional income source can depend on an individual's skills, resources, interests, and goals. Diversifying income streams can enhance financial resilience and open up new opportunities for personal and financial growth.

Tables 4.3 and 4.4 give averages of what HHHs and WiHHs say were their incomes from non-farm income sources. The results show that HHHs from the Central Gonja District earned most of the non-farm income from remittances (GHC998), sale of labour (GHC794), charcoal production (GHC502), salary (GHC500) and food processing (GHC466), while HHHs from the Nabdam District earned most non-farm income from other unspecified sources (GHC4,000), businesses (GHC3,000), small-scale mining (GHC2,135), salary (GHC1,000) and remittances (GHC853). On the other hand, the women from Central Gonja District indicated that their non-farm sources of income included charcoal production (GHC662), food processing (GHC627), sale of firewood (GHC593), transportation services (GHC493), and sale of fruits (GHC317) while women from the Nabdam District earned more from remittances (GHC690), sale of fruits (GHC500), sale of labour (GHC390), petty trading/food vending (GHC285) and sale of firewood (GHC268).

Table 4.3: Breakdown of non-farm sources of income by HHHs (in GHC)

Non-farm income source	Central Gonja		Nabdam		Combined	
	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev
Charcoal Production	502.2	551.3	160.0		452.30	425.7
Food Processing	466.6		576.1	1384.2	519.60	825.9
Gifts	341.4	130.2	117.0	73.50	209.50	219.2
Petty Trading/Food Vending	210.5		236.2	110.0	248.10	162.8
Remittances	998.3		853.1	755.9	797.10	890.5
Salary	500.0		1000.0		750.00	
Sale of Firewood	450.7	228.2	248.2	220.1	432.10	435.3
Sale of Fruits (Shea, Dawadawa, etc.)	290.4	252.6	308.3	525.3	350.40	447.3
Sale of Labour	794.7	248.5	389.5	255.7	564.90	546.8
Transportation Services	393.6	161.8	132.2	137.0	286.70	302.6
Business			3000.0		3000.00	
Illegal/Small Scale Mining			2135.0	343.5	2135.00	846.2
Stone Quarrying			800.0		800.00	
Other (Specify)			4000.0		4000.00	

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 4.4: Breakdown of non-farm sources of income by WiHHs (women) (in GHC)

Other income source	Central Gonja		Nabdam		Combined	
	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev	Value/cash income (mean)	Std Dev
Charcoal Production	661.70	576.4	206.70	40.4	604.80	559.2
Food Processing	626.70	615.8	378.60	503.2	493.10	548.8
Gifts	151.50	143.6	120.00	57.0	141.00	120.1
Petty Trading/Food Vending	274.50	384.6	285.30	251.6	281.00	304.0
Remittances	280.00	353.6	690.00	567.3	641.80	555.0
Sale of Firewood	593.10	458.1	268.30	156.8	475.00	405.9
Sale of Fruits (Shea, Dawadawa, etc.)	316.70	311.3	500.00	462.0	408.30	393.6
Sale of Labour	247.00	264.8	390.00	366.5	318.50	319.7
Transportation Services	493.80	336.4	145.00	120.1	377.50	324.7
Illegal/Small Scale Mining			250.00		250.00	

Source: Field survey, May 2023

The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies was used to obtain robust ranking of major sources of income by HHHs and WiHHs in both the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts to confirm or deny the quantitative figures presented in Tables 4.3 and 4.4. In the Central Gonja District, petty trading/food vending, sale of fruits, transportation services, food processing, and charcoal production were the important sources of non-farm income from the qualitative analysis (Figure 4.1). This is markedly different from the Nabdam District in which sale of labour, sale of firewood, remittances, gifts, and charcoal production were ranked as their main sources of non-farm income (Figure 4.1). In the case of women in Central Gonja District, charcoal production, sale of firewood, transportation services, sale of food, and food processing were ranked as the five most important sources of non-farm income, while in the Nabdam District, petty trading/food vending, remittances, sale of fire wood, sale of fruits, and sale of labour were ranked by the women as their main sources of non-farm income (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.1: HHHs sources of non-farm income

Figure 4.2: WiHH (women) sources of non-farm income

Comparison of the quantitative (Tables 4.3 and 4.4) and qualitative analysis (Figures 4.1 and 4.2) indicate that what households regard (or perceive) as being most important is not necessarily the ones they earn most income from. For instance, the women from Nabdam District ranked petty trading as the most important non-income income source, but in terms of earnings, petty trading is 4th. That could be because most petty trading/food vending is carried out by women throughout the year, hence, regarded as the most important to them. It also is because the income from petty trading is more stable. Whatever the reasons for the divergence between the non-farm income source that earns the most cash and the one perceived to be important, it is clear that a combination of quantitative and qualitative analyses provides more robust analytical information.

4.4 Expenditure by Households

Households in Central Gonja District spend their income mostly on traditional health care for HH members (15%), farm inputs (14%), and food grains (13%). Households in the Nabdam district spend mainly on soup ingredients (25%), orthodox health care for HH members (11%), and farm inputs (10%). Other expended items in both districts include schooling expenses, labour/animal traction/tractor hire, funerals and social activities, transportation, and clothing among others. Table 4.5 shows that households in the study area largely prioritize their spending on farm inputs, health care (traditional and orthodox), and schooling over others. That is not surprising because farming is the main occupation of most households in rural Ghana, especially in the northern part of the country; and since “health is life”, it is ideal to spend on the health of household members. The results also show that households in the study area relatively spend more on education even though primary and secondary education is highly

subsidized in Ghana. That may be due to the increasing falling standards in the quality of education in public schools in the country. This compels many to send their wards to private schools which are quite expensive.

Table 4.5: Household expenditure on various items by men (HHH) and women (WiHH) in 12 months (2022/2023)

Central Gonja District			Nabdam District		
Expenditure Item	HHH	WiHH	Expenditure Item	HHH	WiHH
	Amount per HH per annum (GHC)			Amount per HH per annum (GHC)	
Traditional health care for HH members	932.57	478.50	Soup ingredients	1460.00	572.80
Farm inputs	864.29	388.40	Orthodox health care for HH members	632.14	352.40
Food (grain)	842.00	385.30	Farm inputs	585.00	566.90
Schooling expenses	706.44	597.80	Schooling expenses	583.41	455.70
Orthodox health care for HH members	526.11	381.70	Food (grain)	476.92	351.70
Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	514.64	315.70	Funerals and other social activities	405.56	305.30
Meat and dairy	325.56	0.0	Labour/Animal traction/tractor hire	352.73	376.00
Soup ingredients	318.40	328.20	Remittances/Gifts	300.00	1120.00
Livestock inputs	282.00	1210.00	Transportation (general)	202.86	493.30
Transportation (for farm activities)	265.71	241.70	Livestock inputs	200.00	174.00
Clothing	228.33	234.20	Clothing	200.00	307.90
Transportation (general)	175.00	363.70	Traditional health care for HH members	106.67	529.70
Funerals and other social activities	167.60	226.70	Church & other religious contributions	100.00	514.00
Firewood/Charcoal	156.67	412.00	Sacrifices	100.00	0.00
Sacrifices	470.00		Transportation (for farm activities)	50.00	0.00
Meat and dairy		385.80	Firewood/Charcoal	0.00	390.00
Irrigation water charges			Meat and dairy	0.00	0.00
Remittances/gifts					1120.00

The estimated expenses from WiHH (Table 4.6) indicate that households in Central Gonja spend their income largely on schooling expenses (17%), livestock inputs (12%), and orthodox health care for HH (11%). Results from WiHH in the Nabdam district indicate that household expenses are mostly on soup ingredients (21%), remittances (15%), and schooling expenses (10%). Other expended items in both districts also include farm inputs, food grains, labour/animal traction/tractor hire, funerals and social activities, transportation, and clothing among others (Table 4.5). The estimates from WiHH in both districts generally show that most expended items are schooling expenses, soup ingredients, and food grains. The estimates on schooling are somewhat consistent with HHH, which shows that households in the study area spend substantially on educating household members. While farm inputs and health care expenses dominate in HHH perspectives, WiHH's perspectives vary a bit as the results show that households spend relatively more on soup ingredients and food grains. These differences in opinions are expected because women are largely in charge of cooking (buying food ingredients and grains), hence, they attach more value to those items. On the other hand, the HHH is generally responsible for buying farm inputs and paying for health care expenses, hence, they attach high value and/or importance to them.

CHAPTER 5

HOUSEHOLD FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY

5.1 Household Food Security

5.1.1 Household food adequacy

Shortage of cultivated food is a common occurrence in many households in the survey area. In general, about half of the households experienced a shortage of food (cultivated food) for two consecutive agricultural years (2021 and 2022). Thus, their farm produce did not take them through a year after the previous harvest. Specifically, Table 5.1 indicates that about 52% and 28% of households in the Central Gonja District had shortages of food in 2021 and 2022 respectively. Likewise, 74% and 78% of households in the Nabdam District had shortages in 2021 and 2022 respectively. The shortages were thus more severe in the Nabdam District for both agricultural years. To confirm these shortages, the HHHs were asked whether their households purchased food in the reference years or not. As seen in Table 5.1 about 40% and 24% of households in Central Gonja indicated that their households purchased food in the referenced years. In the Nabdam District, about 59% and 67% of HHH said their households purchased food in the referenced years, a confirmation that food insecurity in the Nabdam District may be higher than that of Central Gonja District.

Table 5.1: Adequacy of Household -Cultivated Food-HHH

Household food security		Central Gonja				Nabdam			
		Yes		No		Yes		No	
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Adequacy of household cultivated food (HHH)	Two years ago (2021)	12	48	13	52	7	25.9	20	74.1
	Last year (2022)	18	72	7	28	6	22.2	21	77.8
Adequacy of household cultivated food (WiHH)	Two years ago (2021)	14	56	11	44	4	16	21	84
	Last year (2022)	12	48	13	52	4	16	21	84
Household purchase of food (HHH)	Two years ago (2021)	10	40	15	60	16	59.3	11	40.7
	Last year (2022)	6	24	19	76	18	66.7	9	33.3
Household purchase of food (WiHH)	Two years ago (2021)	9	36	16	64	16	64	9	36
	Last year (2022)	11	44	14	56	18	72	7	28

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In comparison, a similar proportion of responding women in households in the survey area indicated that their harvests did not take them through a year after harvest for the 2021 and 2022 agricultural years. As seen in Table 5.1, about 44% and 52% of WiHHs from Central Gonja District reported having food shortages in 2021 and 2022 respectively. WiHHs from the Nabdam District indicated a shortage of about 84% in each referenced year. Just as reported by the HHHs, the shortages were more severe in the Nabdam District than in Central Gonja District. WiHHs further confirmed that households had to purchase food to supplement their household needs. About 36% and 44% of WiHHs in Central Gonja, and 64% and 72% of WiHHs in Nabdam District respectively indicated that their households purchased food in 2021 and 2022.

The food insecurity situation appears better in Central Gonja because, as reported by the respondents earlier, many households in Central Gonja are also into transportation businesses as their other sources of income. Central Gonja District has this advantage due to their proximity to the ECOWAS road (N1 highway) which makes it easier for services such as transportation. The Black and White Volta Rivers also pass through Central Gonja, giving them an added advantage of accessing water for dry season farming and fishing. The district also houses a lot of settlers who are mostly into businesses. All these livelihood activities help to boost food security in the area. Harvests from the dry season in particular boost household harvests for the year, hence, a few are likely to run out of food as may be the case in the observed results.

5.1.2 Period of shortage of cultivated food

In both districts, several households had food shortages during the 2021 and 2022 farming years. Within the Central Gonja District, there was a notable surge in the number of respondents who had a shortage of food from January to December 2021. As can be observed from both HHH and WiHH in Table 5.2, many responded to have run out of food in the months of April to September. A similar trend can be observed for the 2022 year in Central Gonja except for January to March where respondents did not have shortages. Conversely, household heads in the Nabdam district experienced food shortages from April to September in both 2021 and 2022. The women in the household however reported experiencing food shortages from January to September, with many reporting to have run out of food within March-September in both farming years. Largely, Table 5.2 indicates that food shortages from household harvests mostly occur between March and September. That explains that October where harvesting mostly occurs, is the month that households are food- secured. Most households stay food-secured for at least three months (October-December) and at most 6 months (October-March).

Table 5.2: Shortages of cultivated food by months in 2021 and 2022

Shortage of Cultivated Food	Central Gonja				Nabdham			
	HHHs		WiHHs		HHHs		WiHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
January	1 (3.2)	0	1 (4.5)	0	0	0	1 (1.4)	1 (1.8)
February	2 (6.5)	0	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	0	0	1 (1.4)	2 (3.6)
March	2 (6.5)	0	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	0	0	3 (4.1)	4 (7.3)
April	4 (12.9)	1 (3)	2 (9.1)	2 (9.1)	7 (9.6)	7 (11.1)	6 (8.2)	7 (12.7)
May	3 (9.7)	2 (6.1)	2 (9.1)	1 (4.5)	7 (9.6)	9 (14.3)	9 (12.3)	11 (20)
June	3 (9.7)	1 (3)	1 (4.5)	1 (4.5)	17 (23.3)	10 (15.9)	17 (23.3)	11 (20)
July	3 (9.7)	5 (15.2)	1 (4.5)	2 (9.1)	17 (23.3)	14 (22.2)	16 (21.9)	11 (20)
August	4 (12.9)	6 (18.2)	2 (9.1)	3 (13.6)	14 (19.2)	12 (19)	15 (20.5)	7 (12.7)
September	3 (9.7)	4 (12.1)	3 (13.6)	4 (18.2)	5 (6.8)	3 (4.8)	5 (6.8)	1 (1.8)
October	2 (6.5)	4 (12.1)	3 (13.6)	4 (18.2)	0	0	0	0
November	2 (6.5)	5 (15.2)	2 (9.1)	1 (4.5)	0	0	0	0
December	2 (6.5)	5 (15.2)	2 (9.1)	1 (4.5)	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

5.1.3. Period of food purchase

Farming households are usually compelled to buy food when faced with a shortage of their cultivated crops. In 2021, a considerable number of household heads in the Central Gonja District did not purchase food in May, October, November, and December (Table 5.3). However, they did engage in food purchases during the other months, with July registering the highest percentage (25%). This heightened purchase activity in July is attributed to many farmers depleting their stored food reserves during this cultivation-intensive period. In 2022, a greater number of households resorted to buying food throughout the year. On the other hand, no household in the Nabdham District made food purchases in January, February, March, October, November, and December in both 2021 and 2022; rather, purchases were made from April to September in both years.

WiHH in the Central Gonja District consistently purchased food from January to December. In contrast, WiHH in the Nabdham district bought food from January to September but refrained from purchasing any from October to December. In summary, the results in Table 5.3 confirm that households in the study area are largely food-secure from October to December. Purchases of food to supplement household requirements, however, occur throughout the year but surges in July and August (just before farm harvests take place).

Table 5.3: Period of food purchases

Period of purchase of food	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HHHs		WiHHs		HHHs		WiHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
January	1 (8.3)	1 (5.9)	1 (2.3)	2 (7.1)	0	0	1 (1.4)	1 (1.5)
February	1 (8.3)	1 (5.9)	2 (4.5)	2 (7.1)	0	0	1 (1.4)	2 (3)
March	1 (8.3)	1 (5.9)	3 (6.8)	3 (10.7)	0	0	4 (5.6)	4 (6.1)
April	2 (16.7)	1 (5.9)	3 (6.8)	3 (10.7)	7 (8.5)	10 (14.3)	7 (9.7)	7 (10.6)
May	0	1 (5.9)	4 (9.1)	1 (3.6)	13 (15.9)	10 (14.3)	9 (12.5)	11 (16.7)
June	1 (8.3)	1 (5.9)	4 (9.1)	3 (10.7)	18 (22)	16 (22.9)	17 (23.6)	14 (21.2)
July	3 (25)	2 (11.8)	6 (13.6)	3 (10.7)	19 (23.2)	14 (20)	16 (22.2)	14 (21.2)
August	2 (16.7)	3 (17.6)	6 (13.6)	3 (10.7)	13 (15.9)	11 (15.7)	14 (19.4)	10 (15.2)
September	1 (8.3)	3 (17.6)	5 (11.4)	2 (7.1)	5 (6.1)	2 (2.9)	3 (4.2)	3 (4.5)
October	0	1 (5.9)	4 (9.1)	2 (7.1)	0	0	0	0
November	0	1 (5.9)	3 (6.8)	2 (7.1)	0	0	0	0
December	0	1 (5.9)	3 (6.8)	2 (7.1)	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

It is quite normal for households to expect food shortages since food shortages are a frequent occurrence. In the Central Gonja District, 64% of household heads anticipated a food shortage in 2023, while 36% expressed no expectation of scarcity (Table 5.4). In the Nabdam district, a majority (70.4%) of household heads did not anticipate a food shortage. Table 5.4 further explains that a significant portion (72%) of WiHH in the Central Gonja district expected a food shortage in 2023. Interestingly, the Nabdam district witnessed a reversal, with about 36% of WiHH expecting a food shortage. This suggests a divergence in food security expectations between the two districts, potentially influenced by higher agricultural engagement or successful harvests in Nabdam compared to Central Gonja.

Table 5.4: Food shortage expectations

Food Shortage Expectation in 2023	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HHH		WiHH		HHH		WiHH	
	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.	Freq.	% Freq.
Expect food shortage	16	64.0	18	72.0	8	29.6	9	36.0
Do not expect a food shortage	9	36.0	7	28.0	19	70.4	16	64.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The primary sources of income for food purchase for most HHHs in the Central Gonja district in both 2021 and 2022 were derived from the sale of cash crops, food crops, and animals; and engaging in petty trading (Table 5.5). In 2021, HHHs in the Central Gonja district also relied on their salaries and credit cash for food purchases. In contrast, women in Central Gonja gathered their income from the sale of cash and food crops, and animals, and engaged in petty trading. It is worth noting that WiHH in the Central Gonja district are not employed with fixed salaries, and none of them received remittances from relatives residing outside their communities. On the other hand, HHHs in the Nabdam District did not use any of their salary money; instead, the majority of their income for food purchases in 2021 and 2022 came from the sale of crops, cash crops, animals, remittances from relatives, petty trade, credit, and other sources (sale of labor). Likewise, WiHH in the Nabdam mostly uses their income from the sale of food crops, the sale of animals, remittances from relatives, petty trading, and credits among others to purchase food for consumption (Table 5.5).

Table 5.5: Sources of income for food purchase

Source of Income	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HHHs		WiHHs		HHHs		WiHHs	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
	Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)		Freq (% Freq)	
Income from salaried work	1 (4.8)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sale of cash crops	6 (28.6)	1 (10)	2 (22.2)	2 (16.7)	1 (4.3)	1 (3.8)	0	0
Sale of food crops	4 (19)	4 (40)	1 (22.2)	1 (8.3)	2 (8.7)	1 (3.8)	1 (3.6)	4 (13.8)
Sale of animals	4 (19)	4 (40)	2 (22.2)	4 (33.3)	7 (30.4)	9 (34.6)	7 (25)	6 (20.7)
Remittances from relatives	2 (9.5)	0	1 (11.1)	0	6 (26.1)	7 (26.9)	8 (28.6)	8 (27.6)
Petty trading	3 (14.3)	1 (10)	3 (33.3)	5 (41.7)	4 (17.4)	4 (15.4)	9 (32.1)	7 (24.1)
Credit (cash or in-kind)	1 (4.8)	0	0	0	1 (4.3)	1 (3.8)	1 (3.6)	1 (3.4)
Other - Sale of labour	-	-	-	-	1 (4.3)	2 (7.7)		
Other							2 (7.1)	1 (3.4)
Business					1 (4.3)	1 (3.8)		

Source: Field survey, April 2023

5.2 Household Dietary Diversity

5.2.1 Dietary intake in the past day-HHH

All household heads (men) in Central Gonja had consumed food made from grains or cereals (primarily maize and rice-based) the day before the interview. Nearly all household heads also consumed foods such as fresh/dried or shellfish (seafood), starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, oil, fat, or butter, and sugar or honey (Table 5.6). The vast majority of household heads in Central Gonja had consumed foods such as condiments, legume-based diets like beans, leafy vegetables like amaranths and Corchorus, and fruits like shea. At least a little over two-thirds of household heads in Central Gonja consumed meat and other organs, while less than half consumed eggs and other dairy products. Dairy products were the least consumed food group by household heads in Central Gonja. All considerable household heads interviewed exhibited high dietary diversity in Central Gonja.

In Nabdam, all HHHs (men) consumed food made from grains or cereals-based diets and vegetables (Table 5.6). Nearly all of them also consumed foods made from oil, fat, or butter. The vast majority (74%) of household heads consumed condiment-based foods and sugar or honey. At least less than two-thirds of household heads in Nabdam consumed fruits, fresh/dried fish/shellfish, legume-based diets like beans, eggs, tuber-based diets, dairy, sugar or honey, and meat and organs. Dairy-based products were the least consumed food group. In Nabdam, a considerable proportion (70.4%) of the interviewed household heads exhibited high dietary diversity, with 11% showing low dietary diversity.

Overall, both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts share similarities in consuming grains/cereals and oils/fats/butter, with a considerable proportion of household heads exhibiting high dietary diversity. However, they differ in terms of seafood consumption, specific food items, and the prevalence of low dietary diversity. In Central Gonja, nearly all household heads consumed seafood, whereas this was not explicitly mentioned in Nabdam. Moreover, the majority of household heads in Nabdam consumed condiment-based foods. Regarding food diversity, household heads in Central Gonja consumed legumes, leafy vegetables, fruits, meat, and dairy products, whereas consumption varied in Nabdam, with less than two-thirds consuming specific items.

The findings suggest that while there are similarities in dietary patterns between Central Gonja and Nabdam, there are also notable differences that should be taken into account when designing nutrition interventions for these areas. A considerable proportion of household heads in both regions exhibit high dietary diversity, indicating a varied and potentially nutritious diet among a significant portion of the population. Notably, there is a difference in seafood consumption between the two regions, with nearly all household heads in Central Gonja consuming seafood. This disparity could be attributed to geographical or cultural factors, suggesting that interventions promoting seafood consumption might be more relevant in Central Gonja.

Additionally, the consumption of specific food items varies between the two regions. For example, condiment-based foods are more prevalent in Nabdam, while a wider variety of foods, including legumes, leafy vegetables, fruits, meat, and dairy products, are consumed in Central Gonja.

Table 5.6: HHHs Dietary Diversity (HDDS)

Food types	Central Gonja(n=25)		Nabdam(n=25)	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal -based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	25	100	25	100
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	23	92	9	33.3
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	20	80.0	22	100.0
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tomborong, baobab, paw paw, Dimbu etc	18	72.0	16	59.3
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	15	60.0	7	25.9
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	6	24.0	3	11.1
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, catfish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	24	96.0	15	55.6
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, e.g “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	18	72.0	10	37.0
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	3	12.0	2	7.4
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	23	92.0	23	85.2
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	23	92.0	5	18.5
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, boabab?	21	84.0	20	74.1
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	0	0.00	3	11.1
Moderate	0	0.00	5	18.5
High	25	100	10	70.4

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The prevalence of low dietary diversity is higher in Nabdam compared to Central Gonja, with 11% of household heads showing low dietary diversity in Nabdam compared to none in Central

Gonja. This indicates a potential area of concern for nutrition interventions in Nabdam, suggesting a need to promote a more diverse diet among its population.

5.2.2 Dietary intake in the past day - WiHHs

In households in Central Gonja, all the women had consumed food made from grains or cereal products, as well as starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, on the day before the interview. Additionally, nearly all of them had consumed foods made from seafood (fresh/dried or shellfish), sugar or honey, and other food condiments such as coffee and dawadawa (Table 5.7). At least two-thirds or more of the women in households in Central Gonja had consumed legume-based diets including beans, vegetables, meat, and organs, as well as oils and fats. Approximately half of the women had consumed fruits the day before the interview, while about 20% had consumed eggs. Dairy products were the least consumed food group at 12%. Notably, in Central Gonja, a significant proportion (96%) of the interviewed women revealed high dietary diversity, while 4% showed medium dietary diversity.

In Nabdam, all women in households consumed food made from grains or cereals-based diets (refer to Table 5.17). Nearly all of them had also consumed foods made from vegetables. At least two-thirds of the women in households had consumed oils and fats, condiment-based foods, and fruits. Additionally, half of the women in households had consumed seafood the day before the interview. However, fewer than 44% of women in Nabdam had consumed tuber-based diets, while 36% had consumed legume-based diets like beans, and 32% had consumed meat and organs, as well as sugar or honey. Dairy-based products and eggs were the least consumed food groups. Notably, in Nabdam, a considerable proportion (64%) of the interviewed women in households showed high dietary diversity, while 4% showed low dietary diversity.

While there are similarities in the dietary habits of women in households in Central Gonja and Nabdam, notable differences reflect regional variations and cultural preferences. Nearly all women in households in Central Gonja had consumed seafood, whereas only half of the women in households in Nabdam had done so, indicating significant differences in seafood consumption habits between the two regions, possibly due to geographic location or cultural preferences. In Central Gonja, all women had consumed starchy staples like root and tuber-based diets, whereas fewer than 44% of women in Nabdam had done so, suggesting a higher reliance on tuber-based foods in Central Gonja, potentially due to the region's soil and landscape allowing for the production of root and tuber crops like yam. Additionally, at least two-thirds of women in Central Gonja had consumed legume-based diets, including beans, vegetables, meat, and organs, compared to only 36% in Nabdam, indicating higher consumption of legumes in Central Gonja, potentially contributing to higher protein intake and dietary diversity.

Table 5.7: Women in household dietary diversity (WiHDDS)

Food types	Central Gonja District(n=25)		Nabdam District(n=25)	
	Freq	%Freq	Freq	%Freq
Cereal based foods [Any bread, porridge, Noodles, biscuits, Nyeleng, pancake, cus cus, mbahal, chackry, or any other foods made from millet, sorghum, maize, rice, wheat, findi or <i>[any other locally available grain]</i> ?	25	100.0	25	100.0
Any yams, cassava, konkonte, potatoes, Cocoyam, porridge, gari, ebeh, plasas soup, or any other foods made from roots or tubers?	25	100.0	11	44.0
Any vegetables, e.g. Okro, cabbage, moringa leaves, green green, mboroch, Amaranthus, sorrel, etc.	16	64.0	24	96.0
Any fruits? E.g. Orange, Mango, bananas, ga-a, ara, kaba, tamarin, guava, tombrong, baobab, pawpaw, Dimbu etc	13	52.0	15	60.0
Any beef, pork, sheep/lamb, goat, rabbit, wild game, chicken, duck, or other birds, liver, kidney, heart, or other organ meats?	17	68.0	8	32.0
Any eggs? Chicken, guinea fowl, ducks, turkey, queles	5	20.0	1	4.0
Any fresh or dried fish or shellfish? Tilapia, bonga, cat fish, lady fish, barracuda, sea snail	23	92.0	14	56.0
Any foods made from beans and/or groundnuts, eg. “Red-red” etc.? Akra, domoda, gine job, cooked beans+cassava+fried fish, cooked beans+bread	19	76.0	9	36.0
Any cheese, yogurt, milk or other milk products? Fresh milk, fermented milk, cow oil,	3	12.0	1	4.0
Any foods made with oil, fat, or butter? Meat stew, fish stew, jollof rice, pancake, fishcake, chackry	16	64.0	16	64.0
Any sugar or honey? Fresh honey, sugar candy	24	96.0	8	32.0
Any other foods, such as condiments, dawadawa, coffee, tea. sobolo, mbormbor, kinkiliba, wonjo, tamarin, boabab?	23	92.0	17	68.0
<i>Dietary Diversity</i>				
Low	0	0.00	1	4.0
Moderate	1	4.0	8	32.0
High	24	96.0	16	64.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

5.2.3 Comparison of HHHs and WiHHs Dietary Diversities in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts

Comparing dietary habits by gender and district in Central Gonja and Nabdam reveals both similarities and differences, shedding light on district or regional variations and cultural influences. In Central Gonja, all household heads (men) consumed grains or cereals, seafood, starchy staples, and other foods like condiments and legume-based diets, resulting in high dietary diversity. In contrast, Nabdam's household heads predominantly consumed grains or cereals, vegetables, oils/fats, and condiments, with lower consumption of specific food groups like seafood and tuber-based diets, leading to slightly lower dietary diversity but still

considerable. Seafood consumption was notably higher in Central Gonja, possibly due to geographic and cultural factors, while tuber-based diets were more prevalent in Central Gonja, likely influenced by agricultural practices and landscape suitability. Moreover, legume consumption was higher in Central Gonja, potentially contributing to greater dietary diversity and protein intake. Despite these differences, both districts depict a degree of dietary diversity, indicating opportunities for improved nutrition. Interventions should consider district or regional nuances to effectively promote dietary diversity and address specific nutritional needs, particularly targeting less consumed food groups like dairy and eggs in Nabdam.

5.3 Wealth and Poverty Status of Households

Household wealth status indicates the ability of households to cope with shocks that they encounter. Respondents were asked to indicate the wealth (or poverty) status of their households. Table 5.8 explains that both HHH and WiHH in Central Gonja perceived their households to be averagely rich (88% HHH and 74% WiHH), while HHH and WiHH in Nabdam perceived their households to be poor (69% HHH and 68% WiHH). Thus, the responses between HHHs and WiHHs did not vary much regarding their perceptions of household wealth status.

Table 5.8: Perception on household wealth ranking by HHHs and WiHHs

Wealth Status	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HHH		WiHH		HHH		WiHH	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Very wealthy (rich)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wealthy (rich)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Averagely wealthy	21	87.5	17	73.9	8	30.8	5	20
Poor	3	12.5	6	24.0	18	69.2	17	68.0
Very poor	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	12

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Respondents were also asked about their perception of the wealth status of community members. Table 5.9 shows that the number of poor people in both districts are more than the other wealth/poverty categorisations as perceived by the respondents. About 20% of HHHs and 23% of WiHHs in Central Gonja indicated that members in the communities are poor while less percentages of both HHH and WiHH indicated that members of the communities can be put in other categories. Similarly, about 43% of HHHs and 51% of WiHHs in the Nabdam District indicated that their community members are poor. This may imply that the severity of poverty is more pronounced in Nabdam compared to Central Gonja, hence, the high rating of poverty in Nabdam. The standard deviations reported for Nabdam are also relatively low (compared to their means), indicating a relatively consistent view of respondents, which may confirm that the poverty rate in Nabdam is indeed high. On the other hand, poverty perceptions from Central Gonja are a bit varied (evidenced by relatively higher Std Devs). On average, the

results from both districts show that arable crop farmers are largely perceived to be poor while salaried workers are perceived to be wealthy. Details of categories of community members that are perceived to be wealthy/poor are presented in Appendix 5.8.

Table 5.9: Perception of wealth status of community members by HHHs and WiHHs

Wealth Status	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HHH		WiHH		HHH		WiHH	
	Mean (%)	Std Dev	Mean (%)	Std Dev	Mean (%)	Std Dev	Mean (%)	Std Dev
Very wealthy (rich)	10.25	18.21	7.74	15.40	1.12	2.877	0.33	1.05
Wealthy (rich)	7.96	12.30	6.96	10.17	4.04	6.33	3.29	7.29
Averagely wealthy	13.96	13.04	20.65	17.04	16.92	13.63	14.21	8.36
Poor	19.63	19.08	23.43	19.84	42.92	21.83	50.96	19.059
Very poor	12.21	13.37	10.92	12.36	35.28	23.60	30.79	19.74

Source: Field survey, April 2023

CHAPTER 6

HOUSEHOLD RESOURCES AND USE

6.1 Land use Changes and Transitions over 5, 10, 30 and 50 years in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts

Tables 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 present descriptions of land use changes/transitions over time by HHHs and WiHHs in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. It is important to note that there are hardly compound farms in the Central Gonja District. As a result, there have not been significant changes over the years with respect to compound farms in the Central Gonja District. As can be seen in all the four tables, Central Gonja responses to compound farms are very few and can be ignored. With respect to the bush farms in Central Gonja, 40% of the land was already cultivated land 5 years ago, 55% 10 years ago, 45% 30 years ago and only 3% 50 years ago, according to HHHs. Most of what was not cultivated were either bareground or grazing land/grassland 5 and 10 years ago, and natural forests/woodland or open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees) 30 and 50 years ago (Tables 6.1 and 6.2). Similar trends were stated by WiHHs (Tables 6.3 and 6.4). A close study of the tables reveals interesting details of the land transitions over time.

In the case of Nabdam District, both compound and bush farms have existed over several decades for almost all households. The land use changes or transitions are, therefore, quite different from the cases in Central Gonja District. According to HHHs, about 65% and 67% of their compound and bush farmlands respectively were already cultivated 5 years ago, and about 53% of both compound and bush farms were cultivated lands 10 years ago. Also, about 53% and 13% of the compound and bush farmlands were cultivated lands 30 years ago, while 50 years ago, 47% of present cultivated land was cultivated and none of the present farms covered by bush farms were cultivated. Careful study of the four tables reveal a lot of interesting details of the land transitions. The changes that have taken place over 50 years indicate the role of human activities in transforming forests, woodlands, grazing lands etc. into cultivated lands in the two districts.

Table 6.1: HHHs description of land use changes/transition over time in Central Gonja and Nabdham Districts – 5 and 10 years

Land Description	5 years ago						10 years ago					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja District												
Cultivated land	1	33	8	40	-	-	2	67	11	55	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	5	-	-
irregular cultivated land	-	-	1	5	-	-	1	33	2	10	-	-
Bare ground	1	33	5	25	1	50	-	-	-	-	1	50
Dam/Dugouts	1	33	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	5	-	-
Open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	-	-	2	10	-	-	-	-	1	5	1	50
Cultivated Trees	-	-	1	5	-	-	-	-	1	5	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	-	-	3	15	1	50	-	-	3	15	-	-
Nabdham District												
Cultivated land	22	64.7	10	66.7	2	66.7	18	52.9	8	53.3	1	33.3
Natural forest/woodland	2	5.9	3	20	-	-	2	5.9	3	20	-	-
irregular cultivated land	1	2.9	-	-	1	33.3	3	8.8	2	13.3	2	66.7
Bare ground	3	8.8	1	6.7	-	-	2	5.9	-	-	-	-
Dam/Dugouts	5	14.7	1	6.7	-	-	5	14.7	1	6.7	-	-
Open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	5.9	-	-	-	-
Cultivated Trees	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	1	2.9	-	-	-	-	2	5.9	1	6.7	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 6.2: HHHs description of land use changes/transition over time in Central Gonja and Nabdham Districts – 30 and 50 years

Land Description	30 years						50 years					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja District												
Cultivated land	2	66.7	9	45	-	-	2	66.7	3	15	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	1	33.3	1	5	2	100	1	33.3	14	70	2	100
irregular cultivated land	-	-	1	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bare ground	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dam/Dugouts	-	-	1	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	-	-	7	35	-	-	-	-	3	15	-	-
Cultivated Trees	-	-	1	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nabdham District												
Cultivated land	18	52.9	2	13.3	-	-	16	47.1	-	-	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	3	8.8	4	26.7	-	-	3	8.8	10	66.7	-	-
irregular cultivated land	2	5.9	4	26.7	-	-	3	8.8	1	6.7	-	-
Bare ground	1	2.9	-	-	-	-	2	5.9	1	6.7	-	-
Dam/Dugouts	6	17.6	1	6.7	-	-	5	14.7	1	6.7	-	-
Open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	1	2.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	6.7	-	-
Cultivated Trees	1	2.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	2	5.9	4	26.7	3	100	1	2.9	-	-	-	-

Table 6.3: WiHHs description of land use changes/transition over time in Central Gonja and Nabdham Districts – 5 and 10 years

Land Description	5 years						10 years					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja District												
Cultivated land	-	-	7	30.4	-	-	-	-	6	26.1	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	-	-	1	4.3	-	-	-	-	2	8.7	-	-
Bareground	2	100	9	39.1	2	100	-	-	5	21.7	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	-	-	2	8.7	-	-	1	50	4	17.4	1	50
Cultivated trees							1	50	1	4.3	-	-
open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	-	-	1	4.3	-	-	2	5.9	1	4.3	-	-
Irregular cultivated lands	-	-	2	8.7	-	-	-	-	4	17.4	1	50
Dams/Dugouts	-	-	1	4.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nabdham District												
Cultivated land	22	68.8	10	66.7	2	66.7	18	56.2	8	53.3	1	33.3
Natural forest/woodland	2	6.2	3	20	-	-	2	6.2	3	20	-	-
Bareground	2	6.2	-	-	-	-	2	6.2	-	-	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	2	6.2	1	6.7	-	-
Cultivated trees							-	-	-	-	-	-
open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Irregular cultivated lands	-	-	1	6.7	1	33.3	3	9.4	2	13.3	2	66.7
Dams/Dugouts	5	15.6	1	6.7	-	-	5	15.6	1	6.7	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 6.4: WiHHs description of land use changes/transition over time in Central Gonja and Nabdham Districts – 30 and 50 years

Land Description	30 years						50 years					
	Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before		Compound farmlands		Bush farmlands		Other lands used before	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja District												
Cultivated land	2	100	13	56.5	1	50	-	-	10	43.5	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	-	-	4	17.4	-	-	1	50	10	43.5	1	50
Bareground	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cultivated trees	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	1	2.9	3	13	-	-	1	50	2	8.7	1	50
Irregular cultivated lands	-	-	1	4.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dams/Dugouts	-	-	2	8.7	1	50	-	-	1	4.3	-	-
Nabdham District												
Cultivated land	17	53.1	2	13.3	-	-	15	46.9	-	-	-	-
Natural forest/woodland	3	9.4	4	26.7	-	-	3	9.4	10	66.7	-	-
Bareground	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	2	6.2	1	6.7	-	-
Grazing land/Grassland	2	6.2	4	26.7	3	100	4	12.5	1	6.7	3	100
Cultivated trees	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	1	3.1	-	-	-	-
open woodlands (shrubs and scattered trees)	1	3.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	6.7	-	-
Irregular cultivated lands	1	3.1	4	26.7	-	-	2	6.2	1	6.7	-	-
Dams/Dugouts	6	18.8	1	6.7	-	-	5	15.6	1	6.7	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

6.2 Disappearance of Natural Resource Items (Loss of biodiversity)

It is common knowledge that over time, several natural resource items have disappeared or are disappearing from various landscapes. Their disappearance implies natural resources degradation, loss of biodiversity and loss of valuable ecosystem services. The sampled men and women farmers in the Central Gonja and Nabdham Districts were asked to identify the causes of these losses and degradation. The question was open-ended (not structured) so the answers given were very diverse. Tables 6.5 and 6.6 give the summaries of the responses by HHHs and WiHHs respectively. Even though the responses (frequencies) are few in several cases, they give good indication of the perspectives of the people (men and women farmers) of the causes of degradation and loss of biodiversity.

Table 6.5: Causes of loss of natural resource items according to HHHs

Causes of loss of natural resource items	Indigenous crops		Indigenous livestock		Indigenous trees/shrubs		Indigenous farming practices		Water bodies/wetlands		Wildlife	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja												
New varieties/breeds	2	11.8	-	-	1	10.0	-	-	-	-	-	0.0
Low yields	1	5.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Soil infertility	2	11.8	2	66.7	-	-	3	27.3	2	33.3	-	-
Bush burning		0.0		0.0	3	30.0	1	9.1	-	-	1	33.3
Deforestation	1	5.9	1	33.3	-	-	-	-	1	16.7	-	-
Climate change	4	23.5	-	-	2	20.0	1	9.1	-	-	1	33.3
Erratic rainfall	1	5.9	-	-	-	-		0.0	-	-	-	-
Modern farming methods/Use of agrochemicals	2	11.8	-	-	2	20.0	2	18.2	-	-	1	33.3
Animal destruction	2	11.8	-	-	1	10.0	-	-	1	16.7	-	-
Other human activities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	16.7	-	-
Community expansion	-	-	-	-	1	10.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Urbanization	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	27.3	-	-	-	-
Lack of knowledge	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	9.1	-	-	-	-
Negligence	2	11.8	-	-	-	-		0.0	1	16.7	-	-
Total	17	100	3	100	10	100	11	100	6	100	3	
Nabdham												
Soil infertility	1	12.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	14.3	0	0.0
Bush burning	1	12.5	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	1	25.0
Deforestation	-	0.0	-	0.0	3	33.3	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Climate change	3	37.5	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	4	57.1	1	25.0
Erratic rainfall	-	0.0	-	0.0	1	11.1	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Modern farming methods/use of agrochemicals	3	37.5	2	66.7	1	11.1	4	80.0	2	28.6	2	50.0
Animal destruction	-	0.0	1	33.3	2	22.2	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Other human activities	-	0.0	-	0.0	1	11.1	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Urbanization	-	0.0	-	0.0	1	11.1	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Lack of knowledge	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	1	20.0	-	0.0	-	0.0
Total	8		3		9		5		7		4	

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Both Table 6.5 and 6.6 show that men and women farmers are very much concerned about the loss of biodiversity. The results indicate their concern for losses in several natural resource items including indigenous crops, indigenous trees/shrubs, indigenous farming systems and water bodies/wetlands featured prominently. The priority concerns of HHHs and WiHHs in both Central Gonja and Nabdam include losses of indigenous crops, indigenous trees/shrubs and water bodies/wetlands. According to the HHHs in Central Gonja District the greatest cause of loss of indigenous crops is climate change (23.5%) while bush burning is the greatest cause of loss of indigenous trees/shrubs (30%) (Table 6.5). They also claim urbanization and soil infertility are the main causes of the loss of indigenous farming systems (27.3%). For Nabdam HHHs, modern farming methods/use of agrochemicals is the greatest cause of loss of indigenous crops, livestock, trees/shrubs, and water bodies/wetlands, followed by climate change. For WiHHs in Central Gonja, soil infertility, climate change, negligence and deforestation are the causes of loss of indigenous crops, while for WiHHs in Nabdam, deforestation and modern farming are the main causes of the loss indigenous trees/shrubs.

Table 6.6: Causes of loss of natural resource items according to WiHHs

	Indigenous crops		Indigenous livestock		Indigenous trees/shrubs		Indigenous farming practices		Water bodies/wetlands		Wildlife	
	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Central Gonja District												
New varieties/ breeds	-	-	-	-	1	16.7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Low yields	1	5.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Soil infertility	5	25.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bush burning	1	5.0	-	-	2	33.3	-	-	-	-	1	50.0
Deforestation	3	15.0	-	-	2	33.3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Climate change	4	20.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Erratic rainfall	1	5.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Modern farming methods/Use of agrochemicals	1	5.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Animal destruction	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	75.0	-	-
Other human activities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	25.0	1	50.0
Urbanization	-	-	-	-	1	16.7	3	100	-	-	-	-
Lack of knowledge	-	-	-	-	1	16.7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Negligence	4	20.0	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	20	100	1	100	7	100	3	100	4	100	2	10-0
Nabdam District												
Bush burning	1	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Deforestation	-	-	-	-	3	42.9	-	-	-	0	-	-
Climate change	1	10	-	-	1	14.3	-	-	5	71.4	-	-
Erratic rainfall	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	20.0	-	-	1	16.7
Modern farming methods/Use of agrochemicals	3	30	-	-	3	42.9	4	80.0	1	14.3	3	50.0
Farming and other human activities	4	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	33.3
Community expansion	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	14.3	-	0.0
Lack of knowledge	1	10.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	10		-	-	7		5		7		6	

Source: Field survey, April 2023

6.3 Reasons for Yields Change Over Time

Yields change over time and the dynamics of agricultural productivity, involves fluctuations in quantity and quality of crops and/or livestock over time. This variability is influenced by factors such as environmental conditions, technological improvements, management practices, and socio-economic factors. Yields, whether crop output per acre or livestock productivity, are seldom consistent.

In the Central Gonja District, HHHs (men) attribute increase in yields over the past 5 years to the use of improved crop varieties, effective crop management, and sound land practices among the male members of households. In contrast, men in the Nabdam district, attribute increase in yields over time to the adequate application of fertilizers or manure and effective land management (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Household heads’ reasons for the increase in yields over time by Districts

In the Central Gonja district, women claim the increase in yields are due to factors such as the use of improved crop varieties, fertile soils, and effective land management, as depicted in Figure 6.2. Women in Nabdam District did not report increases in yields over time. They claim yields have generally declined over the past 5 years.

Figure 6.2 WiHH reasons for an increase in yields over time in Central Gonja District

The decline in agricultural yield can stem from a variety of factors. In the Central Gonja District, HHHs identified poor soil fertility, the presence of pests and diseases, and challenges in weed management as the three primary reasons for the decrease in yields over time. Conversely, in the Nabdam District, the factors contributing to yield reduction, according to HHHs are, unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, and the prevalence of pests and diseases (Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3 Household heads' reasons for the decrease in yields over time by District

For the women, pests and diseases, unreliable rainfall and weed management are the three paramount reasons for the decrease in yields over time in Central Gonja. Financial constraints, weed management, and unreliable rainfall are the main reasons for the decline in yield in the Nabdam district (Figure 6.4).

Figure 6.4 WiHH reasons for decrease in yields by Districts

Poor soil fertility and the incidence of pests and diseases emerge as common challenges among household heads, while weed management and unreliable rainfall are the common challenges among women. Although financial constraint is provided as a reason for the decrease in yield in Nabdam district, there are no marked differences in terms of reasons for a decrease in yield at the district level, albeit the differences only occur at the gender level.

6.4 Land Degradation and Restoration/Rehabilitation

6.4.1 Major causes of land degradation

Though the loss of biodiversity discussed earlier can be regarded as part of land degradation, this section deals with more general causes of land degradation, Farmers were asked to rank five main causes of land degradation (including soil, forest/grassland degradation) in their communities, 1 being the most severe and 5 the least. The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies was then used to obtain the percentage weighted scores as given in Figures 6.5 and 6.6 for HHHs and WiHHs respectively. The weighted frequencies are given Appendix 2.

In both districts, HHHs and WiHHs identified the three most severe causes of land degradation to be deforestation (Charcoal production), bush burning and continuous cropping.

Figure 6.5: Relative causes of land degradation in Districts according HHHs

Figure 6.5: Relative causes of land degradation in Districts according WiHHHs

6.4.2 Rehabilitation of degraded lands

Farmers have been using various method to rehabilitate their degraded lands so they were asked to indicate the methods of rehabilitation that had been very successful (rank 1), successful (rank 2) and not successful (rank 3). The method of weighted scores of ranked frequencies was used to analyse the responses. The method turns the discrete information obtained into continuous information and thus can indicate the level of success in continuous terms. The results are as given in Figures 6.6 and 6.7 for HHHs and WiHHs respectively. Men in Central Gonja identified fallowing and use of organic matter/soil amendments to be successful methods (about 45% and 36% successful respectively) while the men in Nabdam identified use of

organic matter/soil amendments as very successful, about 65% successful (Figure 6.6). Central Gonja men indicated natural regeneration to be about 20% successful and agroforestry to be only about 5% successful. The women of Central Gonja identified fallowing and natural regeneration to be about 58% and 40% successful respectively but organic matter to be only about 5% successful. The women in Nabdam however indicated the use of organic matter/soil amendments to be about 76% successful, natural regeneration about 18%, fallow about 10% and stone bunding about 8% (Figure 6.7).

Figure 6.6: Methods of rehabilitating degraded lands in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts, according to HHHs.

Figure 6.7: Methods of rehabilitating degraded lands in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts, according to WiHHs.

6.5 Use of Inputs and Digital Tools

The use of digital tools to support agriculture and other activities in households is continuing to increase even in the remotest parts of West Africa. This is because small farmers know the importance of adequate and timely information especially with regards to farm level decision making. Thus farmers asked to indicate the digital tools being used by different categories of people in the households.

Tables 6.7 and 6.8 give the different types of digital tools used by men, women and youth as reported by HHHs and WiHHs respectively. Non-smart phones are commonly used by all persons and both HHHs and WiHHs indicate so. There is some level of access to radio and TV but smart phones, as expected, are used by very few men and women but much more by the youth.

The general observation is that useful digital tools that can effectively assist in communication in the communities is yet to be widespread. It is partly due to the limited access to formal education in several parts of the districts.

Table 6.9: Digital tools used by Household Head members as reported by Men (HHHs)

Digital tools	Central Gonja District			Nabdram District		
	Men	Women	Youth	Men	Women	Youth
	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)
Non-smart phones	24 (55.8)	21 (58.3)	22 (47.8)	24 (22.9)	24 (28.6)	24 (22.0)
Radio (access to radio e.g., phones)	6 (14.0)	5 (13.9)	6 (13.0)	22 (21.0)	17 (20.2)	21 (19.3)
Television (TV)	5 (11.6)	4 (11.1)	5 (10.8)	18 (17.1)	15 (17.9)	20 (18.4)
Smartphone (Voice)	1 (2.3)	1 (2.8)	3 (6.5)	7 (6.7)	7 (8.3)	7 (6.4)
Smartphone (Voice and SMS)	1 (2.3)	1 (2.8)	1 (2.2)	8 (7.6)	6 (7.1)	8 (7.3)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS, and WhatsApp)	4 (9.3)	2 (5.6)	6 (13.0)	13 (12.4)	8 (9.5)	15 (13.8)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS, WhatsApp +)	2 (4.7)	2 (5.6)	3 (6.5)	9 (8.6)	5 (6.0)	9 (8.3)
Computer (No email)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (2.9)	1 (1.2)	4 (3.7)
Computer (email)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.0)	1 (1.2)	1 (0.9)
Other (specify)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
None	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 6.10: Digital tools used by Household Head members as reported by Women (WiHHs)

Digital tools	Central Gonja District			Nabdam District		
	Men	Women	Youth	Men	Women	Youth
	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)	Freq (%)
Non-smart phones	20 (57.1)	20 (66.7)	20 (47.6)	25 (29.4)	25 (35.2)	24 (26.1)
Radio (access to radio e.g., phones)	6 (17.1)	5 (16.7)	5 (11.9)	21 (24.7)	17 (23.9)	18 (19.6)
Television (TV)	5 (14.3)	4 (13.3)	5 (11.9)	11 (12.9)	7 (9.9)	12 (13.0)
Smartphone (Voice)	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)	2 (4.8)	8 (9.4)	7 (9.9)	9 (9.8)
Smartphone (Voice and SMS)	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)	2 (4.8)	5 (5.9)	4 (5.6)	10 (10.9)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS, and WhatsApp)	2 (5.7)	0 (0.0)	5 (11.9)	6 (7.1)	5 (7.0)	7 (7.6)
Smartphone (Voice, SMS, WhatsApp +)	0 (0.0)	1 (3.3)	1 (2.4)	7 (8.2)	5 (7.0)	9 (9.8)
Computer (No email)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.1)
Computer (email)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (4.8)	1 (1.2)	1 (1.4)	2 (2.2)
Other (specify)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
None	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

Source: Field survey, April 2023

CHAPTER 7

AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES AND USE OF AGRO-WASTES

7.1 Knowledge and Use of Agroecological Practices

Adopting ecologically sound farming practices is paramount for the sustainability of agriculture. This section delves into the multifaceted sphere of sustainable agriculture, focusing on crucial elements such as the knowledge and use of agroecological practices. It discusses the influencing factors steering the use of these practices, emphasizing their seamless integration into farming systems. Furthermore, the section explores the types and uses of agro-wastes, as well as the quantities generated by households, as integral components in nurturing a holistic and environmentally conscious approach to agriculture.

Agroecological practices play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable agriculture and promoting environmentally friendly and resilient farming systems. Assessing the awareness and usage of these practices at both the Central Gonja and Nabdam districts and discerning nuanced differences between men and women – at the gender level, is crucial for understanding the effectiveness of sustainable farming initiatives as shown in Tables 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, and 7.4.

Central Gonja District

In the Central Gonja district, men (household heads) are primarily aware of and mention various agroecological practices, including crop rotation, crop residue management, mulching, cover cropping, soil bunds, fallow, and the use of early maturing/drought-resistant varieties. Specifically, 48% of men are aware of crop rotation, approximately 20% are aware of crop residue management, and 63% each are aware of mulching and cover cropping. Additionally, 8% are aware of soil bunds and fallow, while only 3% know early maturing/drought-resistant varieties (Table 7.1).

Table 7.1: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central Gonja District

Agroecological technologies	Men (HHHs) (N=25)					
	Awareness		Use in the 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Crop rotation	12	48.0	12	48.0	9	36.0
Crop residues management	5	20.0	5	20.0	5	20.0
Mulching	4	16.0	4	16.0	2	8.0
Cover cropping	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Soil bunds	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Fallow	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Early maturing / drought - resistant varieties	1	4.0	1	4.0	0	0
Green manure e.g., Mucuna	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 7.2: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Central Gonja District

Agroecological technologies	Women (WiHHs) (N=25)					
	Awareness		Use in the 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Crop rotation	11	44.0	11	44.0	10	40.0
Crop residues management	3	12.0	3	12.0	2	8.0
Mulching	3	12.0	3	12.0	1	4.0
Cover cropping	7	28.0	7	28.0	6	24.0
Soil bunds	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Fallow	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Early maturing / drought - resistant varieties	0	0	0	0	0	0
Green manure e.g., Mucuna	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In Central Gonja, the agroecological practices that men are aware of, as mentioned in the survey, align with the information provided in the focus group discussions and key informant interviews. Regarding the use of these agroecological practices, 48% each of men employed crop rotation in the 2022 season or at any time within the past 5 years, respectively. This aligns with the findings in the focus group discussions and key informant interviews. According to male participants in the focus group, crop rotation is mainly used to control pests and diseases, and key informant interviews highlight its role in soil fertility improvement.

Similarly, among the 20% of men aware of crop residue management, the same percentage implemented it as an agroecological practice in the 2022 season. The percentage of men practicing crop residue management in the 2022 season is the same as it was five years ago, with 20% utilizing it in both periods.

Cover cropping and mulching, sharing similar objectives, offer various benefits for sustainable agriculture. Of the 16% of men who are aware of these practices, the same percentage used them in the 2022 season. Notably, there was an 8% decrease in usage of mulching 5 years ago compared to the 2022 season users. According to key informant interviews, mulching is used because of its contribution to soil water retention. Cover cropping, on the other hand, is employed for soil fertility improvement, soil water retention, and erosion control. However, according to key informants, cover cropping is largely practiced because of its ability to improve soil fertility.

The awareness and use of early maturing/drought-resistant varieties as an agroecological practice are relatively recent, with only 4% incorporating them into their farming practices in the 2022 season. Other agroecological practices mentioned based on their usefulness during the focus group discussions and key informant interviews, and not captured by the survey, include minimum tillage, crop-livestock integration, agroforestry, and manure application.

Especially for agroforestry, there was a consensus on its benefits in terms of serving as windbreaks.

For women in the Central Gonja District, the agroecological practices mentioned include crop rotation, cover cropping, crop residue management, mulching, fallow, soil bunds, and green manuring (Table 7.1b). Among these practices, crop rotation is the most recognized, with 44% of women being aware of it. Approximately 12 of the women mentioned that they are aware of cover cropping as an agroecological practice. Twelvepercent each indicated awareness of crop residue management and mulching, respectively. For fallow, soil bunds, and green manuring, 8%, 4%, and 4%, respectively, mentioned them as agroecological practices they are aware of. These findings align with those from the focus group discussions. Additionally, integrated pest management, agroforestry, minimum tillage, and intercropping (mixed cropping), though not mentioned in the survey, were considered important practices by women in the Central Gonja District.

Concerning the usage of these agroecological practices, except for crop residue management and mulching, the usage of all other practices was higher by five percentage points five years ago compared to their use in the 2022 season.

However, the same proportion of women who are aware of these agroecological practices used them in the 2022 season. According to the women participants during the focus group discussions, the benefits they derive from practicing crop rotation, mulching, and cover cropping are not different from those reported by men. Green manuring, a practice solely undertaken by women in the Central Gonja District, involves incorporating *Mucuna* and *Canavalia* into the soil. According to key informant interviews, *Mucuna* and *Canavalia* could "pull nitrogen from the atmosphere and convert it into a form that can be used by plants, thereby enriching the soil with nitrogen—a crucial nutrient for plant growth; outcompete weeds, thereby suppressing their growth; and retain soil moisture".

In the Central Gonja District, awareness of agroecological practices varied based on gender. The findings suggest that, in general, the usage of most agroecological practices among women fluctuated five years ago and the 2022 season in terms of percentages, as compared to men. This could imply a shift in agricultural practices over time or changes in factors influencing women farmers' choices. The exception mentioned for women in crop residue management and mulching, where their usage was not higher five years ago, may have specific implications. It could indicate a growing recognition of the importance of these practices or changes in agricultural strategies to align with current sustainability goals. Lastly, it is worth noting that the same proportion of men and women who are aware of agroecological practices used them in the 2022 season. This may imply that, among households in Central Gonja District, there is a stable and consistent use of these practices over the observed period.

Nabdam District

In the Nabdam District, men (household heads) are primarily aware of and mention over 20 agroecological practices. Key among them are soil bunds, cover cropping, stone bunds/terracing, contour planting, crop rotation, farmyard manure, crop residue management, compost, mulching, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, and burying of weeds. Specifically, 12% of men are aware of soil bunds and cover cropping each. Approximately 36% are aware of stone bunds/terracing, 24% are aware of contour planting, and 20% each are aware of crop rotation and farmyard manure. Additionally, 16% each are aware of crop residue management and compost. Twelve percent of the men are aware of mulching, while 8% each are aware of early maturing/drought-resistant varieties and burying of weeds (Table 7.2a).

Despite the awareness of quite a number of agroecological practices, both the use in five years prior and in the 2022 season are based on the production challenges a particular practice addresses in Nabdam District. Over 32% of men who used soil bunds, 28% used cover cropping, and stone bunds/terracing each in the 2022 season and a 4% increase five years prior did so because of the integral roles these practices play in reducing environmental degradation and fostering long-term agricultural resilience. Soil bunds and stone bunds/terracing play a crucial role in stabilizing slopes, preventing soil erosion, and enhancing water management in hilly or sloping terrains. These practices act as barriers, reducing water runoff to prevent soil loss, while also slowing down water flow, promoting better moisture retention. This is particularly beneficial to farmers in the Nabdam District, as the area is prone to drought or erratic rainfall, making soil bunds and stone bunds/terracing effective measures for sustainable soil conservation.

Other practices utilized in the 2022 season or five years ago by 16 – 24% of men include contour planting, crop rotation, farmyard manure, crop residue management, and compost. According to male participants in focus group discussions, these agroecological practices serve various purposes: erosion control (contour planting), disease and pest management (crop rotation), soil fertility enhancement (farmyard manure and compost), weed control (crop residue management), and overall improvement of soil health. Although intercropping was not explicitly mentioned in the survey, key informant interviews highlighted its significance due to the added benefit of reducing the risk of crop failure. The integration of these agroecological practices into farming systems contributes to sustainable agriculture, reducing dependence on synthetic inputs, promoting biodiversity, and fostering long-term resilience in the face of changing environmental conditions.

During the focus group discussions, male participants also specified the crops commonly used for these practices. Groundnut and maize are typical crops for crop rotation and intercropping, while millet and bean combinations are commonly employed. Beans or cowpea is a typical cover crop used. They emphasized that various crops in the area could be suitable for contour farming.

For women in the Nabdam District, the mentioned agroecological practices include soil bunds, cover cropping, stone bunds/terracing, contour planting, crop rotation, farmyard manure, crop

residues management, compost, mulching, and early maturing/drought-resistant varieties (Table 7.2b). Among these practices, soil bunds are the most recognized, with 40% of women being aware of them. Approximately 32% of women mentioned that they are aware of cover cropping and stone bunds/terracing as agroecological practices. Twenty-eight percent indicated awareness of contour planting. For crop rotation, mulching, farmyard manure, crop residues management, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, and compost, 24%, 20%, 16%, 16%, 16%, and 12%, respectively, mentioned them as agroecological practices they are aware of.

In terms of the usage of these agroecological practices, the same proportion of women who are aware of these practices used them in the 2022 season or five years ago, except for compost, where the usage in the 2022 season was lower by 5%. These findings align with those from the focus group discussions and key informant interviews. Crop-livestock integration, agroforestry, and minimum tillage though not mentioned in the survey, were considered important practices by women in the Nabdam District.

The varying awareness levels for different practices in the Nabdam District among men and women suggest that certain practices have specific relevance in the local context. The fact that soil bunds, stone bunds/terracing, and cover cropping are the most recognized practices among households highlights their importance. The consistent usage of agroecological practices among men and women who are aware of them implies a certain level of integration into their farming practices. This can contribute to sustainability and serve as a foundation for improvement to enhance the resilience of agriculture in the Nabdam District, especially for practices they are aware of but have yet to practice or use.

Table 7.3: HHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Nabdam District

Agroecological practices	Men (HHHs)n=25					
	Awareness		Use in the 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Soil bunds	9	36.0	8	32.0	9	36.0
Cover cropping	9	36.0	7	28.0	8	32.0
Stone bunds/ terracing	8	32.0	7	28.0	8	32.0
Contour planting	6	24.0	5	20.0	6	24.0
Crop rotation	5	20.0	4	16.0	5	20.0
Farmyard manure	5	20.0	5	20.0	5	20.0
Crop residues management	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Compost	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Mulching	3	12.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Early maturing /drought -resistant varieties	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Burying of weeds	2	8.0	2	8.0	2	8.0
Improved water management	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Minimum/No tillage	1	4.0	1	4.0	0	0
Rainwater harvesting (through bunds, zai)	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Zai	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Grass (Vertiver) Strips	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Green manure e.g. Mucuna	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Improved grazing	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Fallow	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Intercropping with grain legumes	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Integrated crop-livestock mgt.	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Basins	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Woodlots	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Agroforestry (trees on the farm)	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	4.0
Lime (Ash)	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Groundwater use (with pumps) for dry-season farming	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Drip Irrigation	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Biochar	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Weather forecasting	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Early warning systems	1	4.0	0	0	0	0
Climate-risk insurance	1	4.0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 7.4: WiHHs awareness and use of agroecological technologies in Nabdam District

Agroecological technologies	Women (WiHHs) n=25					
	Awareness		Use in the 2022 season		Use 5 years ago	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Soil bunds	10	40.0	10	40.0	10	40.0
Cover cropping	8	32.0	7	28.0	8	32.0
Stone bunds/ terracing	8	32.0	7	28.0	8	32.0
Contour planting	7	28.0	7	28.0	7	28.0
Crop rotation	6	24.0	6	24.0	6	24.0
Farmyard manure	4	16.0	3	12.0	3	12.0
Crop residues management	4	16.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Compost	3	12.0	2	8.0	3	12.0
Mulching	5	20.0	4	16.0	4	16.0
Early maturing /drought -resistant varieties	4	16.0	3	12.0	4	6.7
Grass (Vertiver) Strips	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	1.7
Green manure e.g. Mucuna	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	1.7
Intercropping with grain legumes	1	4.0	1	4.0	1	1.7

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts as shown in Tables 7.1 and 7.2, there is a shared awareness of various agroecological practices among men and women. The recognition of practices such as soil bunds and cover cropping underscores a common understanding of their importance for sustainable agriculture. However, the most recognized practices slightly differ, with crop rotation standing out among women in Central Gonja, while soil bunds take precedence among women in Nabdam. Additionally, in Central Gonja, there is a trend indicating lower usage of agroecological practices by women five years ago compared to the 2022 season. This might signify a shift in agricultural practices or changes in factors influencing women farmers' choices. Conversely, in Nabdam, the use of practices like soil bunds, cover cropping, and stone bunds/terracing is driven by the specific challenges these practices address, emphasizing their role in reducing environmental degradation and fostering agricultural resilience.

While Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts share a foundational understanding of the importance of agroecological practices, the nuanced differences in awareness and usage highlight the localized nature of these practices. Recognizing these distinctions is crucial for tailoring interventions that align with the unique needs and environmental conditions of each district, ultimately contributing to the promotion of sustainable agriculture and resilient farming systems.

7.2 Factors Influencing the Use of Agroecological Practices

7.2.1 Factors determining use of soil bunds, Cover crop and crop rotation as agroecological practices

The use of agroecological practices is influenced by various factors, and understanding these elements is crucial for promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural approaches. Tables 7.3, 7.4, and 7.5 showcase three of the most widely used agroecological practices, highlighting key factors that determine their use and implementation across districts and genders. Additionally, Tables 7.8, and 7.9 present influencing factors specific to certain agroecological practices, considering the relevance to particular districts.

In Central Gonja, 25% of men each mentioned the low cost of technology, high expected benefits, and improvement in benefits as influencing factors for using soil bunds as an agroecological practice (Table 7.3). For women in the Central Gonja District, the influencing factors for using soil bunds are related to the infertility of the land (25%), low cost of technology (18%), soil improvement (18%), high expected benefits (11%), low risk (7%), availability of inputs (7%), and low labor (7%). Other influencing factors include the female respondent's technical capability (4%) and secure land tenure (4%).

Table 7.5 Factors influencing the use of soil bunds as an agroecological practice

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Factors influencing use	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)		Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Land is infertile	-	-	7	25	7	26.9	7	23.3
Low cost of technology	1	25	5	17.9	7	26.9	7	23.3
Low risk	-	-	2	7.1	1	3.8	3	10
Availability of inputs	-	-	2	7.1	6	23.1	6	20
Low labour	-	-	2	7.1	1	3.8	-	-
High expected benefits	1	25	3	10.7	-	-	-	-
Improves the soil	1	25	5	17.9	1	3.8	2	6.7
Technically capable	-	-	1	3.6	1	3.8	3	10
Secure land tenure	-	-	1	3.5	1	3.8	2	6.7
Other	-	-	-	-	1	3.8	-	-

In the Nabdam District, 27% of men each mentioned infertility of the land and low cost of technology as the most influencing factors for using soil bunds as an agroecological practice (Table 7.3). Other influencing factors for the use of soil bunds by men included the availability of inputs to carry out the practice (23%), and 4% of the men each mentioned low risk, low labor, soil improvement, technical capability, and secure land tenure. For women in the Nabdam District, the influencing factors for using soil bunds are related to the infertility of the land (23%), low cost of the technology involved (23%), availability of inputs to carry out the practice (20%), low risk (10%), and technical capability (10%).

In both districts, men and women shared certain factors influencing the use of soil bunds, but their priorities varied. While factors like land infertility and technology's cost were consistent, other priorities showed distinctions, with women often considering soil improvement and low risk more than men did. Similarly, men, especially in Nabdam, used soil bunds because of the inputs' availability, contrasting with women who prioritized technical capability and low risk.

The influencing factors for using cover crops as an agroecological practice are shown in Table 7.4. In the Central Gonja District, the majority of men (25% each) were influenced to practice cover cropping due to the low cost of technology, expected benefits, and the improvement it brings to the soil. Others, constituting 13% each, highlighted factors such as land infertility and the availability of inputs.

Table 7.6 Factors influencing the use of cover crop as an agroecological practice

Factors influencing use	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)		Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Land is infertile	1	12.5	4	36.4	8	23.5	7	24.1
Low cost of technology	2	25	-	-	8	23.5	6	20.7
Low risk	-	-	2	18.2	2	5.9	2	6.9
Availability of inputs	1	12.5	-	-	8	23.5	7	24.1
Low labour	-	-	1	9.1	3	8.8	2	6.9
High expected benefits	2	25.0	1	9.1	2	5.9	2	6.9
Improves the soil	2	25.0	3	27.3	1	2.9	1	3.5
Technically capable	-	-	-	-	1	2.9	2	6.9
Secure land tenure	-	-	-	-	1	2.9	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

For the women in Central Gonja, the majority (36%) were influenced to adopt cover cropping as an agroecological practice because their lands were infertile. About 18% utilized it due to its low risk, and 9% each practiced it because of its low labor requirement and the high expected benefits (Table 7.4).

In the Nabdam District, 24% of men each practiced cover cropping because the technology used is low cost, their lands are infertile, and the required inputs are available (Table B13). About 9% of men practiced cover cropping because of the low labor required, while 6% each were influenced to use it because it has low risk and high expected benefits. For women, on the other hand, the majority (24% each) were influenced to practice cover cropping because their lands are infertile, and the required inputs are available. The low cost of technology in

cover cropping influenced about 21% of women in the Nabdam District to use it. The others, 7% each, used cover cropping because of low risk, low labor, and high expected benefits.

Both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts exhibit similarities and differences in the factors influencing the use of cover cropping as an agroecological practice. In both districts, the low cost of technology is a significant influencing factor for men practicing cover cropping. Additionally, the infertility of the land is a common influencing factor for women practicing cover cropping in both districts.

In Central Gonja, men and women share similarities in their influencing factors, emphasizing the low cost of technology, expected benefits, and soil improvement. However, in Nabdam, men were more influenced by the availability of inputs, while women were more influenced by the low cost of technology. In Central Gonja, women placed a higher emphasis on the infertility of their lands (36%), whereas in Nabdam, the infertility of the land was equally influential for both men (24%) and women (24%). The percentage of women influenced by low-risk, low-labor, and high-expected benefits varied between the districts. In Central Gonja, 18% of women each utilized cover cropping due to low risk, and 9% each due to low labor and high expected benefits. In Nabdam, 7% each of women considered low risk, low labor, and high expected benefits as influencing factors.

The influencing factors for using crop rotation as an agroecological practice, categorized by district and gender, are shown in Table 7.5. In the Central Gonja District, the majority of men (23% each) practiced crop rotation because it improved the soil. Additionally, others practiced crop rotation because their lands were not fertile (19%), it is a low-cost technology (16%), and high expected benefits (16%). Similar to Central Gonja, the influencing factors for the use of crop rotation by men in the Nabdam District include improving the soil (28%), low cost of technology (17%), low risk (11%), high expected benefits (11%), and technical capability to implement (11%) are the main factors that determined the use. For the women in Nabdam, improvement of the soil (33%) and infertile land (22%) are the major factors that determined their use. Others include the availability of inputs (11%), high expected benefits (11%), and technical capability (11%).

Both Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts in Table 7.5 exhibit similarities and differences in the influencing factors for using crop rotation as an agroecological practice. While men in both districts share common influencing factors, such as soil improvement and low-cost technology, there are notable distinctions in the factors emphasized by women. These variations suggest differences in local contexts and preferences between Central Gonja and Nabdam.

In Central Gonja, men also consider the fertility of their lands (19%) and high expected benefits (16%) as significant factors for practicing crop rotation. In contrast, men in Nabdam highlight low risk (11%) and technical capability (11%) as additional factors influencing their use of crop rotation.

For women in Nabdam, improving soil fertility is the predominant factor influencing the use of crop rotation. Additionally, women mention the availability of inputs (11%) and technical capability (11%) as contributing factors to their adoption of crop rotation. These findings highlight the dynamics shaping the use of agroecological practices, reflecting the diverse contexts and considerations in each district.

Table 7.7 Factors influencing the use of crop rotation as an agroecological practice

Factors influencing use	Central Gonja District		Nabdam District			
	Men (HHH)		Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Land is infertile	6	19.4	1	5.6	4	22.2
Low cost of technology	5	16.1	3	16.7		
Low risk	1	3.2	2	11.1	1	5.6
Availability of inputs	3	9.7	1	5.6	2	11.1
Low labour	2	6.5	1	5.6	1	5.6
High expected benefits	5	16.1	2	11.1	2	11.1
Improves the soil	7	22.6	5	27.8	6	33.3
Technically capable	2	6.5	2	11.1	2	11.1
Secure land tenure			1	5.6		

Source: Field survey, April 2023

7.2.2 Factors influencing the use of mulching and crop residue management as agroecological practices in Central Gonja District

Mulching and crop residue management are the most utilized agroecological practices in the Central Gonja District. The influencing factors for employing these practices are outlined in Table 7.6. The majority of men engage in mulching due to its low cost of technology (33%), low labor requirements (22%), and soil improvement benefits (22%). Other contributing factors include the availability of inputs (11%) and addressing land infertility. For women, the use of mulching is primarily determined by factors such as the low cost of technology (20%), low risk (13%), low labor requirements (13%), soil improvement benefits (13%), and technical capability (13%) (Table 7.6).

Both men and women share the primary factor of the low cost of technology as a significant influence on their decision to use mulching. Men seem to place more emphasis on soil improvement benefits (22%) compared to women (13%). Men highlight low labor requirements as a crucial factor (22%), while women also consider it important but to a lesser extent (13%). In contrast, men are influenced by addressing land infertility, a factor not explicitly mentioned by women. Conversely, women are influenced by factors like low risk and technical capability, which are not explicitly mentioned as significant factors for men.

Table 7.8: Influencing factors for the utilization of mulching and crop residues in agroecological practices

Factors influencing use	Mulching				Crop residues management			
	Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)		Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Land is infertile	1	11.1	1	6.7	2	22.2	1	25
Low cost of technology	3	33.3	3	20	1	11.1	-	-
Low risk	-	-	2	13.3	-	-	-	-
Availability of inputs	1	11.1	1	6.7	-	-	-	-
Low labour	2	22.2	2	13.3	1	11.1	-	-
High expected benefits	-	-	1	6.7	1	11.1	1	25
Improves the soil	2	22.2	2	13.3	4	44.4	2	50
Technically capable	-	-	2	13.3	-	-	-	-
Secure land tenure	-	-	1	6.7	-	-	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The majority of men engage in crop residue management due to its soil improvement benefits (44%), land infertility (22%), the low cost of technology (11%), high expected benefits (11%), and low labor requirements (11%). For women, the use of crop residue management is primarily determined by factors such as soil improvement benefits (50%), land infertility (25%), and high expected benefits (25%) (Table 7.6).

The findings on the use of crop residue management indicate that both men and women are primarily influenced by the benefits of soil improvement and the low cost of technology in their decision to use crop residue management as an agroecological strategy.

7.2.3 Factors influencing the use of stone bunds/terracing and contour planting as agroecological practices in Nabdam District

Stone bunds/terracing and contour planting are the most utilized agroecological practices in the Nabdam District. The influencing factors for employing these practices are outlined in Table 7.7. Most men engage in stone bunds/terracing due to its low cost of technology (17%) and availability of inputs (17%). Other contributing factors include land infertility (14%), high expected benefits (14%), soil improvement benefits (10%), secure land tenure (10%), low labor requirements (7%), and technical capability (7%). Similarly, women's use of stone bunds/terracing is primarily determined by factors such as the low cost of technology (24%) and availability of inputs (20%). Other factors include technical capability (16%), land infertility (16%), low risk (8%), soil improvement benefits (8%), and high expected benefits (8%) (Table 7.7).

Table 7.9: Influencing factors for the utilization of stone bunds/terracing and contour planting in agroecological practices

Factors influencing use	Stone bunds/terracing				Contour planting			
	Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)		Men (HHH)		Women (WiHH)	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq.
Land is infertile	4	13.8	4	16	5	26.3	6	25
Low cost of technology	5	17.2	6	24	5	26.3	4	16.7
Low risk	1	3.4	2	8	2	10.5	2	8.3
Availability of inputs	5	17.2	5	20	5	26.3	6	25
Low labour	2	6.9	-	-	1	5.3	2	8.3
High expected benefits	4	13.8	2	8	-	-	1	4.2
Improves the soil	3	10.3	2	8	-	-	2	8.3
Technically capable	2	6.9	4	16	1	5.3	1	4.2
Secure land tenure	3	10.3	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Field survey, April 2023

From Table 7.7, both men and women engage in stone bunds/terracing primarily due to the low cost of technology and the availability of inputs. However, men's usage is more influenced by factors such as land infertility (14%), high expected benefits (14%), and soil improvement benefits (10%). In contrast, women place more emphasis on technical capability (16%) and consider factors like land infertility (16%), low risk (8%), soil improvement benefits (8%), and high expected benefits (8%).

Most men, as shown in Table B16, utilize contour planting primarily due to its low cost of technology (26%), land infertility (26%), and the availability of inputs (26%). Other contributing factors for the use of contour planting include low risk (11%) and low labor requirements (5%). For women, the use of contour planting is primarily determined by factors such as land infertility (25%) and the availability of inputs (25%). Other factors include the low cost of technology (17%), low risk (8%), low labor requirements (8%), soil improvement benefits (8%), and technical capability (4%).

In Nabdam, both men and women, as indicated in Table 7.7, predominantly adopt contour planting due to factors such as the low cost of technology and the availability of inputs. However, men's usage is more influenced by factors like land infertility (26%), while women place more emphasis on land infertility (25%). Additionally, men consider low risk (11%) and low labor requirements (5%) as contributing factors, while women consider factors such as the low cost of technology (17%), low risk (8%), low labor requirements (8%), soil improvement benefits (8%), and technical capability (4%). The contrast in emphasis on specific factors reflects variations in preferences and priorities between men and women in the context of contour planting.

7.3 Use of Agro-Wastes

Agro waste, which includes leftover plant materials, crop residues, and by-products, is generated as a by-product of farming and food processing. Tables 7.8, 7.9, 7.10, and 7.11 present the various types of agro waste and their applications in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts, categorized by gender.

Table 7.8 shows the various types of agro waste and their uses in Central Gonja by men (household heads). The types of agro -waste used by men include stovers from cereals, legumes, grasses, animal manure, and kitchen waste. Cereal stovers have diverse uses; they are either used as soil amendments (raw material for composting or mulching), serve as bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, a source of income, and as raw material for local construction by men. The majority (88%) of it is incorporated into the soil or used as mulch. More than half of the household heads use it as the base material for composting and as bedding or feed for livestock. A relatively small portion of men sells cereal stovers for income and use it as a source of fuel for household cooking activities, and as raw material for building.

For legume waste like stovers from cereals, the majority (40%) of it is incorporated into the soil or used as mulch. A significant portion (28%) of the household heads use it as the base material for composting, and a relatively small portion is either sold or used as bedding or feed for livestock (Table 7.8).

Table 7.10 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Central Gonja District

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as a source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as a building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	22	88	3	12	13	52	4	16	13	52	2	8
Legumes	10	40	2	8	1	4	0	0	7	28	1	4
Grasses	3	12	0	0	3	12	0	0	3	12	1	4
Animal manure	4	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	16	0	0
Kitchen wastes	3	12	0	0	3	12	0	0	2	8	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 7.11 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Central Gonja District

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as a source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as a building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	18	72	2	8	8	32	2	8	10	40	0	0
Legumes	10	40	0	0	7	28	0	0	3	12	1	4
Grasses	2	8	0	0	2	8	1	4	1	4	1	4
Animal manure	6	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	12	0	0
Kitchen wastes	1	4	0	0	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Animal manure, grasses, and kitchen waste, though not sold by men, have substantial portions incorporated into the soil as mulch and used as raw material for composting. Grasses are also used as bedding or feed for livestock by men, aside from their use as a building material (Table 7.8).

Table 7.9 shows that women in Central Gonja use agro-waste to meet diverse needs. Cereal stovers, in particular, have various uses such as soil amendments (raw material for composting or mulching), serving as bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, and an income source. The majority (72%) of it is incorporated into the soil or used as mulch. A significant proportion of women use it as the base material for composting and as bedding or feed for livestock. A relatively small portion of women sell cereal stovers for income and use them as a source of fuel for household cooking activities.

For legume waste, most women (40%) incorporate it into the soil or use it as mulch. A significant portion (28%) of women use it as bedding or feed for livestock, and a relatively small portion (12%) as the base material for composting (Table B18). Substantial portions of animal manure are solely incorporated into the soil as mulch (24%) and used as raw material for composting (12%) by women in Central Gonja. Grasses and kitchen waste, though used in relatively small portions, are incorporated into the soil as mulch (Table 7.9).

In Central Gonja, both men and women actively utilize agro-waste for various purposes, with some minor differences in specific applications. The majority of both genders incorporate cereal stovers into the soil or use them as mulch, while women are slightly more involved in using them as the base material for composting. For legume waste, both men and women incorporate it into the soil or use it as mulch, but women are more inclined to use it as bedding or feed for livestock. Animal manure is similarly used by both genders, primarily incorporated into the soil as mulch and used as raw material for composting. Grasses and kitchen waste,

though used in relatively small portions, are incorporated into the soil as mulch by both men and women.

Tables 7.10 and 7.11 showcase the diverse types of agro waste and their applications in the Nabdam District for men (household heads) and women, respectively. In Table 7.10 men utilize stovers from cereals, legumes, grasses, animal manure, waste from abattoirs, and kitchen waste. Stovers from cereals, not being sold, are predominantly used by most men as raw material for composting or mulching (100%), bedding or feed for livestock (96%), a source of cooking fuel (76%), and raw material for composting (84%). A small portion of men (4%) in the Nabdam District use it as building material. Legume waste follows a similar pattern to cereal stovers; 76% of men use it as livestock feed or bedding, 72% as mulch, and 64% for composting, with 8% selling some but not using it as a building material. Regarding animal manure, the majority of men (100% and 96%) use it by incorporating it into the soil or as mulch and for composting, respectively. A small portion (12%) of animal manure is used as feed for livestock. Traditionally, animal manure undergoes a fermentation process to generate weevils/flies, serving as a protein source, especially for fowls (chickens) or guinea fowls.

Table 7.10 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by men in Nabdam District

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as a source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as a building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	25	100	0	0	24	96	19	76	21	84	1	4
Legumes	18	72	2	8	19	76	5	20	16	64	0	0
Grasses	9	36	5	20	12	48	3	12	5	20	11	44
Animal manure	25	100	1	4	3	12	4	16	24	96	4	16
Wastes from abattoirs	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0
Kitchen wastes	17	68	1	4	14	56	1	4	14	56	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Table 7.11 Types of Agro-wastes and uses by women in Nabdam District (n = 25)

Types of Agro-wastes	Uses of Agro waste											
	Incorporate into soil/mulch		Sale		Livestock feed/bedding		Use as a source of fuel (energy)		Composting		Use as a building material	
	Freq.	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq	Freq.	% Freq
Cereals (stovers)	25	100	1	4	22	88	13	52	24	96	1	4
Legumes	19	76	3	12	18	72	1	4	17	68	1	4
Grasses	10	40	2	8	13	52	0	0	3	12	10	40
Animal manure	25	100	0	0	0	0	1	4	23	92	2	8
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kitchen wastes	17	68	1	4	10	40	0	0	16	64	0	0

Source: Field survey, April 2023

Waste from abattoirs is also a significant agro waste, although it is incorporated into the soil and used for composting to a lesser extent. Similarly, kitchen waste, like legumes, is substantially used for soil amendments, including incorporation into the soil, feeding livestock, and composting (Table 7.10).

Table 7.11 shows that women in the Nabdam District use agro-waste for various purposes. Cereal stovers serve several significant roles, including soil amendments (incorporation into the soil or use as mulch, raw material for composting or mulching), serving as bedding or feed for livestock, a source of fuel for cooking, an income source, and as a building material. Most women in Nabdam use it primarily for amending soils and livestock bedding, with a relatively small portion selling it or using it as a building material.

For legume waste, most women in Nabdam use it as a soil amendment, both as soil mulch (76%) and as raw material for composting (68%), as well as for livestock feed or bedding (72%). A relatively small portion (12%) of women sell their legume waste, and others (4% each) use it as a source of fuel and building material (Table 7.11). Animal manure is mainly used by women as soil mulch (100%) and for composting (92%). A few others (8%) use animal manure as a binder during local constructions and/or as a source of fuel, especially cattle waste. Grasses and kitchen waste are mostly used as soil mulch, livestock feed, and raw material for composting. A relatively small portion of women in Nabdam (8% and 4%) sell grasses and kitchen waste for income (Table 7.11).

Tables 7.10 and 7.11 illustrate the utilization of various types of agro-waste among men (household heads) and women, respectively, in the Nabdam District. Men make use of several types of agro-waste, including stovers from cereals, legumes, grasses, animal manure, and kitchen waste. Conversely, women in the Nabdam District do not utilize agro-waste from abattoirs.

The observations from Tables 7.8 to 7.11 highlight both the commonalities and subtle distinctions in the practices of utilizing agro waste between men and women in Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts. Both men and women actively utilize agro-waste for various purposes. In both districts, cereal stovers are predominantly used by both genders, either by incorporating them into the soil or using them as mulch. Legume waste is similarly used by both men and women, primarily incorporated into the soil, or used as mulch.

In Central Gonja, men are slightly more involved in using cereal stovers as a base material for composting compared to women, while this distinction is the reverse in Nabdam. In Central Gonja, women are more inclined to use legume waste as bedding or feed for livestock compared to men, while in Nabdam, almost the same percentage of men and women use legume waste as bedding or feed for livestock. Neither gender uses agro-waste from abattoirs in Central Gonja, whereas in Nabdam, men utilize agro-waste from abattoirs, which is not used by women in that district. The use of grasses and kitchen waste as agro waste is noted in both districts, but in Central Gonja, it is mentioned to be used in relatively small portions, while significant portions are used by men and women in Nabdam. Although Central Gonja has more grasses comparatively, the relatively small portion of users could be attributed to limited education for both household heads and women in Central Gonja.

7.4 Quantities of Agro Waste Generated by Households

The quantities of agro-waste generated by households play a significant role in understanding the environmental impact of agricultural activities and the potential for recycling or reuse. Table 7.12 provides the average quantities of agro-waste generated by household heads and women per acre per season in the Central Gonja and Nabdam districts.

In Central Gonja, the average quantity of stovers from cereals generated by men is 28.5 with a standard deviation (SD) of 15.6. That of legume waste generated is 34.1 with an SD of 15.6. For women in the same district, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated is 28.8 with an SD of 24.7, and legume waste is 28.4 with an SD of 12.8. Men and women, on average, produce a comparable quantity of cereal stovers, with men contributing slightly less than women in Central Gonja. However, the higher standard deviation for women (24.7) indicates a greater variability in the quantities of cereal stovers generated by women. In terms of legume waste, men, on average, generate a higher quantity compared to women. Consequently, both groups exhibit a moderate level of variability in the quantities of legume waste generated, as indicated by the standard deviation.

Table 7.12 Quantities of agro waste generated per acre per season

Types of Agro wastes	Central Gonja District				Nabdam District			
	Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated		Men quantity generated		Women quantity generated	
	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev
Cereals (stovers)	28.5	15.6	28.8	24.7	48.2	30.1	47	24.5
Legumes	34.1	15.6	28.4	12.8	30.4	18	30.8	19.7
Grasses	0	0	0	0	2.5	3.5	0	0
Animal manure	0	0	0	0	18.3	7.6	25	35.4
Wastes from abattoirs	0	0	0	0	15	7.7	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0	25.7	38.4

Source: Field survey, April 2023

In Nabdam District, the average quantity of stovers from cereals generated by men is 48.2 with a standard deviation (SD) of 30.1. That of legume waste generated is 30.4 with an SD of 18. The average quantities of grasses, animal manure, and waste from abattoirs are 2.5, 18.3, and 15 with an SD of 3.5, 7.6, and 7.7. For women in the same district, the average quantity of cereal stovers generated is 47 with an SD of 24.5, and legume waste is 30.8 with an SD of 18. The average quantities of animal manure, and other waste sources are 25 and 25.7 with an SD of 35.7 and 38.4.

On average, both men and women in Nabdam generate similar quantities of cereal stovers and legume waste. The standard deviations for both cereal stovers and legume waste indicate variability in the quantities generated, suggesting diverse agricultural practices or varying land sizes among households. Men, on average, generate a relatively low quantity of grasses but a higher quantity of animal manure and waste from abattoirs compared to women. The standard deviations for these waste types suggest varying practices among men, while women exhibit more consistency in waste generation.

Furthermore, women, on average, generate higher quantities of animal manure, and other waste sources compared to men. The substantial standard deviations indicate significant variability in waste generation practices among women.

From Table 7.12 Both districts exhibit similarities in the generation of cereal stovers and legume waste. However, differences emerge in other waste types, highlighting variations in waste generation practices, especially among women. Women consistently produce higher quantities of waste across various waste types, demonstrating more uniformity in waste generation practices, as indicated by lower standard deviations. Men in Nabdam generate more cereal stovers but less legume waste compared to Central Gonja.

Chapter 8

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES

8.1 Evidence of Climate Change

There is a wealth of scientific evidence supporting the existence of climate change. In the communities surveyed, the most compelling evidence of climate change in the Central Gonja and the Nabdam districts is evidenced by increased temperature as perceived by the respondents (Figures 8.1, 8.2, 8.3 and 8.4)⁴. For the Central Gonja District which has a wetter climate the least evidence is seen in dried up swamps while the least in Nabdam a drier climate, the respondents perceived increased floods to be less of an evidence of climate change, and markedly, the respondents did not see an increase in crops species to be an outcome of climate change. The least perceived event reinforces our knowledge that water resources are more abundant in Central Gonja and therefore may be available for farming. In the Nabdam district, a much drier climate floods are less encountered.

Figure 8.1: HHH Evidence of climate change by District

⁴ Data from which all these figures have been derived are available. They will not be put in the Appendix to reduce the volume of the report

Figure 8.2: WiHH Evidence of climate change by District

For the women in the household, the evidence of climate change is seen in increased temperatures as was reported by the male household heads and in both communities. For the Central Gonja district the least reported evidence is an increase in floods and for Nabdam district, the least reported evidence is in the change in the types of crops grown.

Figure 8.3: HHH Evidence of climate change- Both districts combined

Ghana, like many other countries, is experiencing the impacts of climate change. The effects are diverse and affect various sectors, communities, and ecosystems. For the two districts combined, the greatest evidence of climate change is evidenced by the increase in temperature. Identifying the single greatest evidence of climate change is challenging because climate change is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon with various interconnected indicators and experienced differently depending on the vulnerability of the person reporting. However, some compelling pieces of evidence that underscore the reality of climate change that the world has been is attributed to temperature changes. The consistent and widespread increase in global temperatures over the past century is a robust indicator of climate change as reported by the IPCC. Record-keeping through temperature measurements from various sources consistently shows a warming trend.

Figure 8.4: WiHH Evidence of climate change – Both districts combined

Similar to the evidence presented by the males, the women reported temperature increases as the greatest evidence of climate change. Change in crop species from all the districts and across sexes do not see an increase in crop species to be evidence of climate change. It would be fair to say that the consequences of climate change are perceived to be negative.

8.2 Climate Change Adaptation Measures

Adaptation measures against climate change involve strategies and actions that help communities, ecosystems, and societies cope with the impacts of a changing climate. These measures aim to reduce vulnerability and enhance resilience. Adaptation is a crucial component of broader climate change response efforts. In the Central Gonja district, the main adaptation strategies are the use of crop diversification/mixed cropping, agroforestry, and planting of trees/windbreaks (woodlots) as ways to counteract the effects of climate change. In the Nabdham

District, the main adaptation measures are planting of trees/windbreaks (woodlots), crop diversification/mixed cropping, and irrigated agriculture. . Interestingly, climate risk insurance was the least known adaptation measure.

Figure 8.5: HHH climate adaptation/mitigation measures by District

Climate change adaptation and mitigation measures in Ghana are seen to be in the planting of trees and woodlots that serve as windbreaks. It is important to note that in the two districts, strong winds are characteristic of the savanna ecosystem and may account for the reason why the respondents viewed planting trees to be the greatest adaptation measure

Figure 8.6: HHH climate adaptation/mitigation measures – Both districts combined

Figure 8.7: WiHH climate adaptation/mitigation measures by District

For the women, in both districts, agroforestry was seen as the most important climate adaptation/ mitigation measure followed by planting trees/woodlots. The least adaptation measure in the central Gonja District was drought resistant crop varieties while in the Nabdam district, the least was seen as climate risk insurance. When the information of the two districts were combined, agroforestry was given a premium with climate risk insurance as the least (Figure 8.8).

Figure 8.8: WiHH climate adaptation/mitigation measures – Both districts combined

8.3 Anti-Environmental Practices

The sustainability and preservation of the natural environment are adversely affected by anti-environmental practices and can vary from person to person. Table 8.1 presents the results of the prevalence of anti-environmental practices in Central and Nabdam districts by household heads and women in households respectively.

Table 8.1: Anti-environmental practices for HHH and WiHH by District

Anti-Environmental Practices	Central Gonja				Nabdam			
	HH		WiHH		HH		WiHH	
	Freq	% Freq.	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq	Freq	% Freq.
Deforestation (Illegal logging/charcoal making and firewood cutting)	18	41.9	17	48.6	20	23	23	31.1
Bush burning (fires)	12	27.9	9	25.7	20	23	15	20.3
Burning of farm residues	6	14	6	17.1	14	16.1	14	18.9
Use of agrochemicals in farms (especially weedicides)	6	14	2	5.7	10	11.5	8	10.8
Use of agrochemicals in water bodies	0	0	0	0	4	4.6	2	2.7
Illegal/small-scale mining	0	0	0	0	11	12.6	9	12.2
Sand winning/stone quarrying	0	0	1	2.9	6	6.9	3	4.1
Unknown	1	2.3			2	2.3		
Total	43	100	35	100	87	100	74	100.1

Source: Field survey, April 2023

The result from household heads shows that deforestation ,illegal logging, charcoal making, and firewood cutting is the number one anti-environmental practice in both districts followed by bush burning, burning of farm residues, and use of agrochemicals. It is important to note that some practices are unique to a particular district. For example, although Central Gonja does not engage in illicit mining, stone quarrying, or the use of agrochemicals in water bodies, Nabdam has high rates of these activities.

Figure 8.9: Anti-Environmental Practices by HHH

The results from women in household show that deforestation is the preceding anti-environmental practice in both Central Gonja and Nabdam. This is followed by bush burning, burning of farm residues, and use of agrochemicals especially weedicide and sand winning. The results for household heads and women in households in this regard are quite similar. Further analyzing the survey results from both districts it's interesting to note that three households from both districts said anti-environmental practices were unknown in these districts. To add to that, anti-environmental practices were not many in the Central Gonja compared to the Nabdam district. The use of agrochemicals in farms especially weedicides is slightly higher in the Nabdam district amongst household heads and women in households as compared to Central Gonja district. Regarding the use of agrochemicals in water bodies in the Central Gonja district are 0but 4.6% and 2.7% for household heads and women in households respectively

Figure 8.10 Anti-Environmental Practices by WiHH

CHAPTER 9

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

9.1 Summary and Conclusions

The baseline study was carried out in the Central and Nabdam Districts of Ghana. The results show that most of the respondents and thus farmers are relatively young and have considerable experience in farming: an average experience of about 23 years in Central Gonja and 27 years in Nabdam. Other factors remaining constant, a youthful population, that has considerable experience in farming, is likely to be more eager to try new ideas and adopt progressive technologies especially technologies that build on their indigenous knowledge.

The livelihood of the people in both districts is critically linked to agriculture. Arable crop farming is the main occupation for all (men and women), in both districts. Livestock and tree crop farming are the main minor occupations for men in the Central Gonja District, while livestock and arable crop farming are the main minor occupations for men in the Nabdam District. In the case of women, the main minor occupations are livestock farming, tree produce processing, and petty trading/food vending in the Central Gonja District, and petty trading/food vending in Nabdam District.

On average, farm sizes are 17.2 acres, 9.7 acres, and 3.2 acres for household (HH), individual men, and individual women farms respectively in Central Gonja District and 4.6 acres, 1.6 acres, and 1.4 acres respectively in Nabdam District. Most farmers in both districts acquired their farmlands through inheritance. Customary land tenure arrangements are the accepted tenure system in both districts. Women, however, do not normally inherit land except in special cases. The commonest method of land preparation in Central Gonja District is the use of a tractor and it is the use of bullock/donkey plough and hoe in the Nabdam District. Farmers in the Central Gonja District do not have “compound farms”. All their farms are “bush farms” since they are located some distance from homesteads..

Most of the farmers in Central Gonja District (about 61.0%) indicated that their farms were averagely fertile and required external inputs and manure every year. In the case of Nabdam District, 43.9% of the farmers perceived their farms to be averagely fertile and requiring external inputs and manure every year. Inorganic fertilizers are used in both districts. While organic fertilizer is hardly used in Central Gonja (about 7.3% of plots), the percentage number of plots to which organic fertilizer was applied in Nabdam District was 88.1%.

The common crop mixtures on farms are maize/groundnut-cassava in the Central Gonja District and millet-sorghum-rice-maize-groundnut-beans in the Nabdam District. The crop mixtures in the Central Gonja District are largely cereal/legume/root, and largely cereal/legume/vegetable in the Nabdam District. Generally, maize, groundnut, millet, rice, and sorghum are the five most important and/or grown crops in the study area. These five crops

dominate and are considered important because they serve as both cash and staple crops. Most households in both districts use high-yielding indigenous seeds that are readily available to them from their own storages.

In Central Gonja, both men and women own various types of livestock. The livestock breeds commonly reared in both districts are indigenous (local breeds). The main constraints faced by farmers in both districts concerning livestock production include diseases, theft, and a lack of feed during the dry season.

Incomes obtained from crop farming are generally very low, averaging about 3,772 GHC and 1,633,37 GHC per acre per season in Central Gonja District and Nabdam District respectively. Petty trading/food vending, sale of fruits, transportation services, food processing, and charcoal production are the other important sources of income in CGD and in ND, respondents ranked the sale of labour, sale of firewood, remittances, gifts, and charcoal production as their other sources of income. Shortage of cultivated food is a common occurrence in most households in the survey area. About half of the households experienced a shortage of food for two consecutive agricultural years (2021 and 2022). Both male and female respondents in Central Gonja perceived their households to be averagely rich (88% HHH and 74% WiHH), while those in Nabdam perceived their households to be poor (69% HHH and 68% WiHH). This indicates that the severity of poverty is more pronounced in Nabdam compared to Central Gonja.

The results show that there has been a significant loss of indigenous crops and trees in both districts; and a significant change in crop yields over time. The decline in agricultural yield stems from a variety of factors. In the Central Gonja District, poor soil fertility, the presence of pests and diseases, and challenges in weed management are identified as the three primary reasons for the decrease in yields over time. The factors contributing to yield reduction in the Nabdam District are associated with unreliable rainfall, poor soil fertility, and the prevalence of pests and diseases.

In the CGD, households are aware of and mention various agroecological practices, including crop rotation, crop residue management, mulching, cover cropping, soil bunds, fallow, and the use of early maturing/drought-resistant varieties. Regarding the use of these agroecological practices, 40% and 38% of men employed crop rotation in the 2022 season or at any time within the past 5 years respectively. In the Nabdam District, households are aware of and mentioned over 20 agroecological practices. Key among them are soil bunds, cover cropping, stone bunds/terracing, contour planting, crop rotation, farmyard manure, crop residue management, compost, mulching, early maturing/drought-resistant varieties, and burying of weeds. Both men and women use all these practices depending on the particular need at a time.

Both districts exhibit similarities in the generation of cereal stovers and legume waste. However, differences emerge in other waste types, highlighting variations in waste generation practices, especially among women. Women consistently produce higher quantities of waste

across various waste types, demonstrating more uniformity in waste generation practices. Men in Nabdam generate more cereal stovers but less legume waste compared to Central Gonja.

Climate change is perceived to be a real occurrence in both districts. The main evidences of climate change include increased temperature, decreased rains, increased draughts, and change in rainfall patterns. The most important climate change adaptation measures as perceived by both men and women in both districts are crop diversifications/mixed cropping, agroforestry, and planting of trees/windbreaks (woodlots).

9.2 Recommendations

1. Most of the respondents (HHs and WiHHs) were relatively young and have considerable experience in farming in both districts. They should be targeted since they are more likely eager to try new ideas and adopt progressive technologies especially technologies that build on their indigenous knowledge.
2. MACCLI (Manure-Agroforestry-Compost-Crop/Livestock Integration) agroecological technique should be adopted for all the districts. The practices are complementary and synergistic. The technique also covers almost all the areas CIRAWA proposes as agroecological solutions, namely compost/vermicompost, household energy production, soil rehabilitation and reclamation (phytoremediation) and others. Households should be empowered technically and otherwise to adopt the technique (preferably in whole but can be in parts).
3. Other agroecological practices that should be promoted include crop rotation, crop residue management and intercropping with legumes, due to their low cost and high expected benefits.
4. Innovative rainwater and irrigation water management should be co-created with farmers. Drip irrigation should be encouraged due to its efficient water use. It is also a method that appeals to youth.
5. Small mechanical tools and equipment that suit agroecological practices need to be produced. Neither the tractor nor hoe are appropriate mechanization tools or equipment for agroecological production.
6. Our engagements and dialogues with stakeholders at national, sub-national, local and community levels lead to the production of a National Agroecological Strategy Plan to redirect national endeavours toward sustainable agricultural and food systems. Agroecology is clearly the path to a viable and sustainable agricultural strategy for smallholder farmers. An agroecological plan for the country is in line with the CIRAWA aim at effective dialogue with national, sub-national and local level stakeholders, visibility of EC funding in the countries and ensuring the project's legacy (WP6). This could be follow-ups after CIRAWA.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: The method of Weighted Scores of Ranked Frequencies (WSRF)

Relative importance of crops (qualitative analysis) - Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts – HHHs

Step 1: Obtain frequencies for the ranks (from respondents)

Central Gonja District						Nabdam District					
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
	Frequencies						Frequencies				
Rice	3	0	0	0	0	Millet	17	5	1	2	1
Maize	12	8	0	0	0	Sorghum	6	7	4	1	1
Groundnut	4	13	12	0	0	Rice	3	4	7	8	4
Soybean	0	1	2	6	0	Maize	0	10	13	1	3
Yam	4	1	4	1	0	Groundnut	0	0	0	7	5
Cassava	1	2	3	6	1	Beans (cowpea)	0	0	0	7	1
Sweet Potato	0	0	0	1	1	Soybean	0	0	0	0	8
Tomato	0	0	0	1	0						
Okro	0	0	0	0	7						
Bambara beans	1	0	0	0	0						
Pepper	0	0	0	0	1						

Source: Field survey April 2023

Step 2: Weight the frequencies to obtain weighted scores

Central Gonja District							Nabdam District						
	1	2	3	4	5	Weighted Scores		1	2	3	4	5	Weighted scores
	Weighted frequencies							Weighted frequencies					
Rice	3x5	0x4	0x3	0x2	0x1	15	Millet	17	5	1	2	1	113
Maize	12x5	8x4	0x3	0x2	0x1	92	Sorghum	6	7	4	1	1	73
Groundnut	4	13	12	0	0	108	Rice	3	4	7	8	4	72
Soybean	0	1	2	6	0	22	Maize		10	13	1	3	84
Yam	4	1	4	1	0	38	Gnuts				7	5	19
Cassava	1	2	3	6	1	35	Beans				7	1	15
Sweet Potato	0	0	0	1	1	3	Soybean					8	8
Tomato	0	0	0	1	0	2							
Okro	0	0	0	0	7	7							

Bambara beans	1	0	0	0	0	5							
Pepper	0	0	0	0	1	0							

Step 3: Obtain the percentage weighted scores

Central Gonja District			Nabdam District		
Crop	Weighted scores	% Weighted scores	Crop	Weighted scores	% Weighted scores
Rice	15	5	Millet	113	29
Maize	92	28	Sorghum	73	19
Groundnut	108	33	Rice	72	19
Soybean	22	7	Maize	84	22
Yam	38	12	Gnuts	19	5
Cassava	35	11	Beans (cowpea)	15	4
Sweet Potato	3	1	Soybean	8	2
Tomato	2	1			
Okro	7	2			
Bambara beans	5	2			
Pepper	0	0			
Total	328	100	Total	384	100

Step 4: Draw the percentage weighted scores diagram

Appendix 2: Causes of land degradation according to HHHs and WiHHs

Rank (1 to 5 Most severe to least severe)- HHH

Main cause	Central Gonja		Nabdam	
	Weighted Freq	%	Weighted Freq	%
Bush burning	93	27.5	78	20.0
Deforestation/Charcoal making	81	24.0	71	18.2
Continuous cropping	53	15.7	64	16.4
Wrong tillage	24	7.1	7	1.8
Improper fertilizer use	20	5.9	44	11.3
Sand winning	17	5.0	22	5.6
Rapid urbanization	17	5.0	10	2.6
Wrong use of agrochemicals	16	4.7	21	5.4
Invasive species	11	3.3	16	4.1
Wrong disposal of plastic waste	6	1.8	24	6.2
Illegal/small scale mining	-	-	25	6.4
Soil Erosion	-	-	5	1.3
No Fertilizer	-	-	3	0.8

Rank (1 to 5 Most severe to least severe)- WiHH

Main cause	Central Gonja		Nabdam	
	Weighted Freq	%	Weighted Freq	%
Bush burning	64	18.0	82	22.0
Deforestation/Charcoal making	88	24.7	79	21.2
Continuous cropping	63	17.7	51	13.7
Wrong tillage	25	7.0	17	4.6
Improper fertilizer use	26	7.3	45	12.1
Sand winning	23	6.5	17	4.6
Rapid urbanization	32	9.0	17	4.6
Wrong use of agrochemicals	7	2.06	5	1.3
Invasive species	12	3.4	18	4.8
Wrong disposal of plastic waste	6	1.7	12	3.2
Illegal/small scale mining	10	2.8	27	7.3
Soil Erosion	-	-	-	-
No Fertilizer	-	-	-	-

Causes of land and soil degradation Central Gonja - HHH

Causes	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th		Total Weighted Freq	Total (%)	Rank
	Frequencies								
Bush burning	13	6		2			93	27.5	
Deforestation/ Charcoal making	9	6	2	2	2		81	24.0	
Illegal/ small scale mining									
Sand winning		1	4		1		17	5.0	
Continuous cropping	1	6	6	2	2		53	15.7	
Improper fertilizer use		2	2	2	2		20	5.9	
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)		1	3	5	1		24	7.1	
Wrong disposal of plastic waste		1		1			6	1.8	
Rapid Urbanization			1	5	4		17	5.0	
Wrong Use of Agro-chemicals			4	1	2		16	4.7	
Invasive species			1	2	4		11	3.3	
Other (Specify									

Causes of land and soil degradation - Nabdam - HHH

Causes	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th		Total Weighted Freq	Total (%)	Rank
	Frequencies								
Bush burning	8	5	4	1	4		78	20.0	
Deforestation/ Charcoal making	8	3	4	2	3		71	18.2	

Illegal/ small scale mining	1	1	2	5			25	6.4	
Sand winning	3			2	3		22	5.6	
Continuous cropping	3	8	3	4			64	16.4	
Improper fertilizer use	2	5	4		2		44	11.3	
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)			1	1	2		7	1.8	
Wrong disposal of plastic waste		1	3	4	3		24	6.2	
Rapid Urbanization		1		2	2		10	2.6	
Wrong Use of Agro-chemicals		1	3	3	2		21	5.4	
Invasive species		1	1	2	5		16	4.1	
Soil Erosion	1						5	1.3	
No Fertilizer			1				3	0.8	

Causes of land and soil degradation - Central Gonja - WiHH

Causes	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th		Total Weighted Freq	Total (%)	Rank
	Frequencies								
Bush burning	5	6	4		3		64	18.0	
Deforestation/ Charcoal making	11	7	1	1			88	24.7	
Illegal/ small scale mining	1		1	1			10	2.8	
Sand winning	2	1	1	2	2		23	6.5	
Continuous cropping	3	4	8	3	2		63	17.7	
Improper fertilizer use	2	3		1	2		26	7.3	
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)		2	2	4	3		25	7.0	
Wrong disposal of plastic waste		1		1			6	1.7	
Rapid Urbanization			5	6	5		32	9.0	
Wrong Use of Agro-chemicals			2		1		7	2.0	

Invasive species				4	4		12	3.4	
Other (Specify									

Causes of land and soil degradation) Nabdam- WiHH

Causes	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th		Total Weighted Freq	Total (%)	Rank
Frequencies									
Bush burning	12	3	1	2	3		82	22.0	
Deforestation/ Charcoal making	4	11	3	2	2		79	21.2	
Illegal/ small scale farming	3		3	1	1		27	7.3	
Sand winning	1		2	2	2		17	4.6	
Continuous cropping	4	5	3		2		51	13.7	
Improper fertilizer use	1	4	6	3			45	12.1	
Wrong tillage (use of heavy machinery)		1	3	2			17	4.6	
Wrong disposal of plastic waste			1	3	3		12	3.2	
Rapid Urbanization		1		4	5		17	4.6	
Wrong Use of Agro-chemicals				2	1		5	1.3	
Invasive species			3	3	3		18	4.8	
Soil Erosion					1		1	0.3	
Stone Quarrying					1		1	0.3	

L 1.5 & 1.7 Methods used to rehabilitate degraded lands - HHH

Level of success (1= very successful, 2= successful 3 = not successful)

Land Rehabilitation Methods	Central Gonja District					Nabdam District				
	Weighted scores					Weighted scores				
	1	2	3	Total	Score %	1	2	3	Total	Score %
Natural regeneration	3	12	0	15	20%	9	2	0	11	18%
Fallow	21	12	0	33	44%	0	6	0	6	10%
Agroforestry	0	2	0	2	3%	0	0	0	0	0%
Organic matter/ soil amendments	21	4	0	25	33%	21	16	3	40	67%
Stone bunding	0	0	0	0	0%	3	0	0	3	5%

Methods used to rehabilitate degraded lands - WiHH

Level of success (1= very successful, 2= successful 3 = not successful)

Land Rehabilitation Methods	Central Gonja District					Nabdam District				
	Weighted scores					Weighted scores				
	1	2	3	Total	Score %	1	2	3	Total	Score %
Natural regeneration	3	18	0	21	40%	6	8	0	14	25%
Fallow	9	20	0	29	56%	0	2	0	2	4%
Agroforestry	0	0	0	0	0%	0	0	0	0	0%
Organic matter/ soil amendments	0	2	0	2	4%	24	16	1	41	72%
Stone bunding	0	0	0	0	0%	0	0	0	0	0%